

A review of different methods to find and date wild boar carcasses in different countries

Enetwild Consortium¹, Vada R.², Broz L.³, Citterio C.⁴, Obber F.⁴, Ferroglio E.², Gómez M. A.⁵, Hahn N.⁶, Knauf S.⁷, Kreutzer M.⁸, O'Mahony K.³, Platovšek Z.¹⁰, Pokorny B.¹⁰, Sauter-Louis C.⁷, Staubach C.^{8,9}, Campana S.⁵, Arseni M.⁵, Zanet S.², Vicente J.⁵.

¹<https://enetwild.com/>, ²Università di Torino, Italy; ³Czech Academy of Sciences, Czech Republic; ⁴Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale delle Venezie, Italy; ⁵Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha, Spain; ⁶WILCON-Wildlife Consulting, Gomadingen, Germany; ⁷Institute of Epidemiology, Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut, Federal Research Institute for Animal Health, Greifswald - Insel Riems, Germany. ⁸Institute of International Animal Health/One Health, Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut, Federal Research Institute for Animal Health, Greifswald - Insel Riems, Germany; ⁹Professorship for One Health/International Animal Health, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Justus Liebig University, Giessen, Germany; ¹⁰Faculty of Environmental Protection, University of Primorska, Slovenia

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Abstract

The detection, removal and disposal of wild boar carcasses in areas affected by African Swine Fever (ASF) is key to understanding disease persistence and improving the effective management of risk. This report reviews different methods of finding and dating wild boar carcasses, considering the factors that affect their effectiveness and practical application in the field. We assessed these issues based on peer-reviewed scientific literature, gray literature, and interviews with government agencies and wildlife professionals in organisations and networks across Europe. Two decades after the introduction of African Swine Fever Virus genotype II in Europe, systematic descriptions of the best methods, available protocols, or detailed guidance remain limited. However, relevant research has recently been conducted in Central Europe addressing the two evaluated issues. Carcass search methods can be broadly categorized into four main types: (i) targeted patrols in areas likely to host wild boar carcasses; (ii) systematic grid searches of a defined area; (iii) the use of detection dogs; and (iv) drone-assisted searches. In our sample, the latter three methods were the most frequently employed, with similar levels of representation. Among the relevant sources identified for assessing carcass dating methods, 36% were based on experimental and controlled studies, while the remainder relied on observational data with limited or no experimental control. Most sources adapted previously published methodologies focused on the direct morphological assessment of the decomposition process, typically providing a stage-based classification of carcass decay rather than a precise temporal estimate. Direct carcass observation was employed either alone or in combination with additional approaches such as camera trapping, metabolomics, entomology, and histological

analysis. Field trials are needed to test the effectiveness of carcass searches and the precision of carcass dating, as well as to adapt and validate methodologies in different European contexts. This review of various carcass detection and dating methods highlights the diversity of approaches used in different countries, emphasising the preliminary nature of the research and the need for further investigation and field trials.

Key words: ASF management, surveillance, wild boar carcass, forensic dating, early detection, freedom of disease

Correspondence: biohaw@efsa.europa.eu

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Summary

Background

In areas affected by African swine fever (ASF) in wild boar populations, wild boar carcasses represent a potential source of infection for other wild boars or domestic pigs that may come into contact with them. The presence of infected carcasses enables the ASF virus to persist even after the wild boar population has been reduced to very low numbers. Therefore, detecting and removing carcasses in ASF-affected areas is an essential strategy for reducing ASFV transmission. Additionally, detecting infected carcasses in new areas helps to define infected areas and follow outbreaks evolution.

In areas affected by or at high risk of ASF, carcass dating is essential to quickly and accurately estimate the *post-mortem* interval (PMI). This provides insights into the potential date of ASF introduction and informs disease control strategies, such as determining the extent of restriction zones or claiming freedom from disease. However, there is a lack of systematic, practical guidance on how to implement the best possible strategies that can be transferred and adapted to specific scenarios in order to optimise the efficacy of carcass searches and the precision of carcass dating.

Objectives

This report aims to review different methods to find wild boar carcasses under different scenarios, and the methods to date those carcasses, considering different factors determining their efficacy and practical application in the field.

Methods

We conducted a review of indexed scientific and grey literature, as well as interviewing administrations and wildlife network professionals across Europe. The systematic literature review first involved creating search strings and defining inclusion and exclusion criteria. These were applied after the articles were screened by topic, title and abstract. The selected articles were then screened in full for further refinement. We also used the snowballing method to find additional papers by following citations from included papers. National veterinary and wildlife authorities were interviewed and requested grey literature/protocols (not available as indexed literature) on the two issues in question, as well as protocols from international networks of wildlife veterinarians (in the case of carcass dating). Data were extracted from the selected papers and interviews and entered into a database in order to describe and compare different approaches, and to list the main factors that need to be considered when defining the best possible methods and practical strategies for different scenarios.

Results

Wild boar carcass search: Overall, 95 documents and/or interviews/questionnaires were collected that potentially included relevant information on carcass search methods and protocols, their characterisation, and the factors that may impact the findability of such carcasses. Sixty of the 95 documents passed the inclusion filter and provided a description (more or less detailed) of the main methods used to search for wild boar carcasses: 1) prospective patrols in sites favourable for the presence of dead wild boars; 2) systematic combing of an area; 3) dog detection; and 4) the use of drones. Most of the items corresponded to indexed literature (n = 29) and interviews (n = 22), while grey literature (usually in the form of blogs, technical reports and unpublished presentations) and questionnaires were less well represented. Given the limited availability of data sources, a maximal inclusion approach was adopted, incorporating all sources deemed useful for addressing each specific question—whether originating from published literature, interviews, or grey literature—regardless of their type. As expected, the majority of items originated from ASF-affected European countries, namely Germany, Italy and Poland. Relevant information

was also collected from outside Europe to a lesser extent, particularly from South Korea and other South-East Asian countries. These documents mostly referred to ASF-infected areas or their immediate surroundings (within 10 km), and to a lesser extent to ASF-free areas. In terms of spatial considerations, we found a similar number of items relating to focal outbreaks and large areas of ASF progression.

The predominant selection criteria for the area in which to search for wild boar carcasses within the data sources were the likelihood of wild boar presence, proximity to risk (e.g. the border with other ASF-affected countries), and previous notification of wild boar mortality. The area covered per wild boar carcass detection event and per day varies according to the method used, ranging from 6 to 750 hectares, with a modal value of 100 hectares.

Parameters to evaluate the performance of wild boar searches were rarely reported, and the methods used varied greatly, making it difficult to compare studies, experiences and methods. While an experimental study was able to compare the number of carcasses found with the number hidden, in real scenarios the number of carcasses is usually unknown. In some cases, numerical expectations were derived from models. In some cases, numerical expectations have been derived from theoretical models. Although performance estimates can be expressed relative to the wild boar population, these population estimates may be unreliable and do not account for local variations in mortality.

Of the data gathered from field surveys aimed at locating wild boar carcasses, 28 surveys presented detailed information on the application and results of carcass search methods and protocols. Data sources were mainly indexed research and grey literature, with only one item being an interview (from Piedmont, Italy; the remaining interviews only provided general data). These surveys came from eight countries and covered ten different experiences, with one to six surveys each (specific trials by method with more or less aggregated data). Only two of these experiences presented different methods: one in Germany, which presented data on combing, dogs and drones; and one in France (on the border with Belgium), which presented data on surveys using patrols, combing and dogs separately. Therefore, the available information is scarce, incomplete and unharmonized, which may prevent a more detailed description and assessment of methods and strategies. Nevertheless, it is valuable, as we detail below, as relevant recommendations could be distilled from the reviewed literature. We found that the effort applied to finding wild boar carcasses varied considerably. For example, the average number of people in teams participating in surveys ranged from five to ten people in most cases. The area screened per team per day also varied widely, from a few hectares (ha) to almost 1000 ha, with most values around 100–200 hectares per team per day. In terms of person per day, the screened surface ranged from a few hectares to 50 hectares, peaking in frequency at 15–20 hectares. The average distance travelled per day was 5.6 km, with most values falling between 2 and 3 km. The average speed was mostly between 0.25 and 0.75 km/h, with some values above 1 km/h when dogs were used. Dogs were employed both to complement human efforts in searching for wild boar carcasses and as an effective standalone method when trained dogs were utilized. Estimations of the number of retrieved carcasses relative to the estimated wild boar population in the area varied widely, but these are probably not very accurate and are likely to be biased. This is mainly due to the generally unknown size of the current wild boar population.

Regarding the description of the data collected from surveys on the search for wild boar carcasses using different methods, we are aware that the number of relevant surveys is limited when it comes to characterising performance and logistical issues depending on the method. Not all of the data that we aimed to collect was collected for all of the surveys (data on effort and efficiency were an exception). We present figures showing the area screened by a team per day and the distance travelled (in km) per event and per day by a team for different

methods, which show that this distance tended to be lower for combing. We also present the travelled distance (km) per event and per day by teams participating in wild boar carcass search activities for different methods. Even when the screened area and travelled distance seemed to be lower for combing, this approach is generally more labour-intensive.

We collected information on the main factors reported as determining the applicability and performance of different wild boar carcass search strategies; to provide evidence on their relative importance (i.e. how frequently these factors were reported in our survey). The most frequently reported factors in our sample were: 1) knowledge of local wild boar ecology, density and spatial corridors; 2) economic compensation; 3) the use of trained sniffer dogs; 4) the coordination of administrations and continuous monitoring/feedback; 5) weather and season; 6) local environmental characteristics (e.g., vegetation) affecting carcass detectability; and 7) the use of different complementary methods. It is evident that the relevance of different factors is context specific and depends on the local scenario and applied methods. We compiled recommendations mainly from indexed papers and from questionnaires. In some cases, the effort applied was determined, but the lack of detailed information and the use of different metrics prevented comparisons between methods, designs (e.g. grid-based vs habitat), strategies, areas and epidemiological scenarios, as well as determining real efficacy in terms of the proportion of carcasses found. The latter could only be addressed through experimental trials. However, due to the comparable nature of the landscape and wild boar ecology across its distribution range, the presented strategies could potentially be adapted for Central and Southern Europe to facilitate the search for infected carcasses according to local conditions.

Dating of wild boar carcasses: A total of 48 documents were collected, including 43 research papers, three questionnaires, one book and one PhD thesis. Two items of different nature (presentations) were also initially screened. A total of 48 documents were collected, including 43 research papers. Of these, 11 were selected for further evaluation of carcass dating methods, as they either specifically addressed wild boar or described methods originally developed for other species but later adapted for application to wild boar. However, all references were screened in detail and the data were included in the data set, since they could provide relevant, directly transferable information for the evaluation of carcass dating methods in wild boar. For instance, this included references to other species (wildlife, pigs, humans), as well as references incorporating carcass PMI estimations into epidemiological models (e.g. several reports by EFSA). Three of these studies were conducted in areas infected with ASF in Europe, specifically in regions classified as Atlantic, Continental and Alpine (mainly Central Europe). However, comparable studies from other temperate regions were conducted in South Korea (n = 4).

Of the eleven documents focusing specifically on wild boar, four were classified as experimental, meaning that wild boar carcasses were used in controlled experiments to evaluate the decay process with rigorously known PMI. In contrast, the remaining seven sources evaluated carcass dating methods based on field observations, where the exact PMI was unknown. From a different point of view, two of the eleven references were original meaning that the authors developed their own methodology to determine PMI in wild boar carcasses. The remaining 9 sources applied or adapted methodology that had already been described using human or other animal models. The methodological approaches most frequently described were based on the following original sources: Megyesi et al. (2005) assessing PMI on human remains, either alone or in combination with other references, in four cases; Goff (2009) (human remains); Anderson and Laehroven (1996) (pig's carcasses); and Parsons and Keough (2009) (pig's carcasses). Several studies adopted Probst et al. (2020) (wild boar carcasses), which in turn relied on Megyesi et al. (2005, adapted).

The most frequently used approach was the direct macroscopic description of the decay/decomposition process, which normally included categorisation into different stages over time, either alone or in combination with other approaches. Macroscopic changes were also frequently monitored using camera traps. Metabolomics, entomology and histology were used to a lesser extent in our sample. Usually, one method was applied to date wild boar carcasses (most frequently macroscopic evaluation), but some studies applied up to five methods to address carcass dating. Different phases of decomposition were determined based on macroscopic evidence, variably according to the study. Therefore, the number of categories of decomposition used was also variable. The number of such categories all over the process (not only at early stages) were more frequently classified into four categories well represented by this terminology: fresh, early decomposition, advanced decomposition, and skeletonization/mummification. In addition, three studies scored the decomposition process based on methodology developed by Brooks et al 2018, Megyesi et al. (2005), and a further adaptation to wild boar by Probst et al. (2020).

Among the various parameters described during the decomposition process, season and habitat or microhabitat conditions were the most frequently considered factors in the selected studies. Environmental temperature and accumulated degree-days (ADD)—reflecting the total heat exposure and insolation affecting the carcass—were also commonly taken into account, along with the influence of scavengers on the decay process. Other factors, such as body size (or age as a proxy) and insect activity, were considered less frequently. Quantification of decomposition in terms of days was possible primarily in experimental studies or those focusing on the early post-mortem stages. For later stages of decomposition, field observations provided PMI estimates expressed more broadly in days, weeks, or months.

Discussion

Regarding wild boar carcass search:

- Despite the crucial importance of removing wild boar carcasses as soon as the first cases are detected in an area (and during subsequent stages), there is a noticeable lack of protocols and guidelines for locating these carcasses.
- This scarcity of protocols and guidance on searching for wild boar carcasses indicates the need to publicise and share what is already known locally based on experience, particularly regarding ASF outbreaks across Europe.
- Relevant research has been conducted in Central Europe in relation to wild boar carcass searches and dating. Further testing and adaptation of these studies in different biogeographical and epidemiological scenarios is needed to assess their efficiency in carcass search and carcass dating, and to determine their adaptability to different scenarios in Europe.
- In Europe, most of the literature on this subject originates from countries affected by ASF. Most national veterinary administrations responded that no systematic protocol for searching for wild boar carcasses exists. We advocate agreeing on and incorporating detailed guidance on wild boar carcass searches as part of the wild boar population control and monitoring plan requested by the Commission from countries as part of the fight against ASF.
- The priority criteria used in the literature we surveyed to select areas for searching for wild boar carcasses are mainly related to the increased risk of finding dead wild boars and the estimated risk of ASF. The optimal approach may involve integrating different strategies to maximise effectiveness. Habitat-based strategies are more efficient in targeted areas where wild boar activity is known, whereas grid-based strategies provide comprehensive coverage and are useful in areas where habitat data is limited. Features usually considered

for a habitat-based strategy include the presence of primary forest types, proximity to water sources, terrain and areas with minimal human disturbance.

- A significant obstacle to developing carcass search strategies based on existing knowledge is the limited available data. Furthermore, the effectiveness of wild boar searches is rarely quantified, and when it is, the methods and metrics employed are often not comparable. The ratio of found to hidden carcasses is mostly unknown. Another relevant issue with the current data is the scarcity of method comparisons, particularly fair comparisons under similar conditions.
- Guidance is needed on the efforts and resources required to be deployed over time. The parameters provided here offer some direction in determining the necessary human effort.
- The main factors reported in the literature that determine the applicability and performance of different wild boar carcass search protocols are of a different nature. The relevance of these factors depends on the local scenario and the methods applied; even a given factor may diminish or increase efficacy under different circumstances.
- Surveillance and search techniques, such as active ground searches by humans or aerial surveillance, are far from 100% effective. While this review identified four main methods for the active detection of wild boar carcasses, an integrated approach could improve the efficiency and effectiveness of surveillance efforts, particularly in hard-to-reach areas:
 - Ground survey teams may work alongside other surveillance tools, such as drones equipped with thermal imaging cameras and carcass-detection dogs.
 - Specifically, patrolling known or potential hotspots for wild boar activity or death beds by car (risk-based surveillance) complements more systematic searches conducted by teams of searchers, drones and dogs. This is particularly useful for the initial, preliminary estimation of the infected area, after which more systematic search activities can be developed.
 - Searching for carcasses with specially trained dogs is an effective method, even in closed vegetation environments and for small carcasses. Well-trained dogs are arguably the most portable and versatile carcass detection tools in use today.
- Further integration and generalisation of the use of drone technology in wildlife surveillance is a promising yet still unexploited area. Drones equipped with thermal imaging cameras have been used to monitor wild boar populations, improving surveillance and containment efforts in hard-to-reach areas and offering the potential for the rapid, efficient and safe detection of wild boar carcasses.

The following experimental areas require further development to generate reliable, practical data for decision-making across various situations and contexts:

- Comparative search studies should assess the effectiveness of different detection methods. Such trials need to be designed to allow results to be compared across different areas using consistent or standardized metrics.
- The probability of detecting a wild boar carcass within a given area must be quantified. This involves placing carcasses with a known location in the field and conducting repeated searches to estimate detection rates.
- The performance of trained detection dogs should be evaluated in diverse habitats and under varying weather conditions, to assess how environmental factors and carcass decomposition stages influence detection success.
- Further research is needed on the integration of technology, particularly drone systems, to compare the efficiency of aerial and ground-based searches and to develop automated wild boar detection capabilities.

As for wild boar carcass dating:

www.efsa.europa.eu/publications

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Determining PMI in wild boar is highly context-specific, depending on factors such as habitat and climatic conditions, and is thus exceptionally challenging. Apart from some experimental studies (i.e. studies with known PMI), there are no validated, adapted protocols or detailed guidance on dating wild boar carcasses during an active outbreak that can be used across all European regions and environments. Although known experiences from Central Europe can be adapted for use in other areas, regional studies with a similar methodology are still required.

- The recent development of methods such as metabolomics-based approaches is promising, but further development, as well as the appropriate facilities and expertise, is required for rapid assessment.
- Estimated post-mortem interval (PMI) using “classical” forensic techniques still presents a wide range of uncertainty based on experimental studies, with this range increasing as time elapses since death.
- Decomposition stages, which are mostly based on macroscopic evidence, cannot be universally associated with specific PMI, as this depends on the specific context and conditions. Due to the complexity of the factors involved, models or automatic algorithms to estimate PMI for wild boars may probably only be precise locally.
- Season, habitat and microhabitat conditions were the most frequently considered factors impacting PMI, body size (or age as a proxy) and insect activity and scavengers.
- The main considerations that need to be accounted for when determining the PMI in wild boar across Europe are: (i) extreme environmental variability, meaning that extrapolating data from studies in different areas/bioregions is probably unreliable; (ii) aspects related to specific decomposition processes in wild boar; (ii) extrapolating data from human studies or even from domestic pigs is also unreliable; (iii) unpredictable scavenger and insect activity, which is characteristic of a given area or bioregion; and (iv) the fact that accessing and analysing wild boar carcasses in remote locations often requires fieldwork, entomological analysis or lab support. The development and validation of new methods based on an understanding of the changes that occur in metabolomics post-mortem are promising, as is the combination of different approaches.

To summarize, determining the PMI in wild boar requires a variety of experiments to be conducted in various environmental settings to build a comprehensive understanding of PMI across Europe, including decomposition studies, and controlled environmental studies. This will also provide the necessary baseline data for forensic pathologists and ecologists dealing with wild boar carcasses.

1. Introduction

1.1. Systematic search, dating and removal of wild boar carcasses is critical to eradicate African swine fever

African swine fever (ASF) is a highly contagious and deadly disease that affects domestic pigs, as well as wild pigs in Eurasia and Asia. It is transmitted through direct contact with infected animals, carcasses or contaminated materials such as food and equipment. Beyond animal health, ASF causes severe economic losses to the pork industry and related sectors in Europe, mainly due to trade restrictions. The disease persists within wild boar populations and, given the limited effectiveness of current control strategies, poses a significant threat to the EU's entire livestock sector, particularly pig farming. Crucially, despite intensive research, a vaccine is not yet available.

One of the *ENETWILD-2* project's key objectives is to contribute to assessing the control of ASF spread in wild boar populations. In accordance with the strategic approach to the management of ASF for the EU (SANTE/7113/2015 – Rev. 12), EFSA previous scientific opinion defines the pathway(s) to achieve ASF freedom in specific areas and recommend criteria for defining an area as free from ASF in wild boar. In carrying out this task, EFSA will consider the outcomes of searching for wild boar carcasses (with identification of the PMI) and the results of testing for the virus (in particular, antibody detection and virus identification). Active surveillance of wild boar involves hunting and testing healthy animals. The main aim is to measure the proportion of infected animals in the susceptible population in order to assess changes in the prevalence of infection. According to the latest EFSA report, published on 30 January 2020, active surveillance can provide indications on the effectiveness of ASF control measures in reducing the prevalence of infected animals, and pave the way for the design of an 'exit strategy' (EFSA, 2021). In order to explore options for an 'exit strategy', the Commission intends to instruct EFSA to evaluate all the necessary elements and specific prevalence measurements (through active and passive surveillance).

The control of ASF in wild boar populations has mainly relied on a combination of carcass removal (systematically searching for and destroying carcasses), culling wild boars (reducing population density through controlled activities) and constructing fences to limit movement and the spread of disease. Early detection of ASF in wild boar populations is essential for controlling the spread of the disease in this scheme. Prompt detection of the virus increases the chances of localising the outbreak, reducing negative economic consequences and potentially reversing the situation. Additionally, risk assessments and epidemiological evaluations benefit from data identifying ecological corridors through which the virus can spread. This allows targeted and effective disease control strategies to be implemented, focusing resources on areas where the risk of ASF is higher rather than implementing costly, broad-scale measures across entire regions. Similarly, determining the absence of ASF in wild boar populations is important for trade and safeguarding domestic pig populations.

Once the presence of ASF in wild boar populations has been confirmed, a critical component of any response strategy is the systematic search for and removal of wild boar carcasses in order to control and eradicate the disease. When the virus is detected, authorities must promptly establish a provisional infected zone, restrict access to forests, ban hunting activities and initiate intensive searches for dead wild boar. The priority then shifts to carcass search and

removal. At this stage, allocating human resources and defining the optimal search strategy is paramount to the success of interventions. Carcass search efforts are usually labour-intensive and require dedicated personnel for active searches, effective organisation, and available protocols. This allows for informed zoning, which is accompanied by movement restrictions, to contain the spread. This includes the creation of infected and buffer zones. These zones are usually adjusted based on the evolution of the epidemic and involve measures such as fencing, bans on forest access and controlled hunting, which are intended to reduce wild boar populations and limit disease transmission. Throughout the epidemic control process, evidence from carcass searches will inform measures and be essential to achieving the ultimate goal of eradication and lifting all related restrictions. Even when not resulting in extensive carcass removal, active surveillance for wild boar carcasses in areas adjacent to outbreak zones or along the expanding disease front can provide critical epidemiological data. This information is vital for monitoring the spatial and temporal progression of the epidemic, informing risk assessments and guiding the prioritisation of control measures. After more than one-decade since ASF firstly impacted central Europe, detection and removal of wild boar carcasses have been proved to be pivotal in controlling the ASF outbreak, and therefore the allocation of sufficient and competent human resources and the implementation of rigorous measures emphasize the relevance of proactive carcass management in ASF eradication strategies.

1.2. Wild boar carcass search

In areas where ASF is present, infected carcasses pose a significant risk of ongoing transmission, particularly in European regions with low environmental temperatures where carcasses persist for longer (Probst et al., 2017; 2019). The presence of ASF-contaminated carcasses enables the virus to persist even after the wild boar population has been reduced to very low numbers. Although ASF is not as contagious as FMD or CSF, for example, it is thought that this pathway may be more important for the spread of ASF than direct contact between live infectious individuals. Models suggest that reduced hunting effort is required in intensive hunting areas in the event of an ASF outbreak, provided carcass removal is implemented in the core area (Lange et al., 2018). Therefore, carcass detection and removal in ASF-affected areas could be an effective strategy for eliminating sources of the virus in the environment and reducing ASF transmission (EFSA et al., 2018; Morelle et al., 2019).

For instance, an active search for carcasses and their systematic removal in accordance with biosecurity procedures were essential for controlling the epidemic in the Czech Republic and Belgium. This was made possible by optimal stakeholder commitment.

Evidence from Europe and elsewhere indicates that the detection of wildlife carcasses in natural areas is often hindered by the terrain being difficult to access and/or carcasses being difficult to see, particularly for human searchers. Although carcass localisation has been tested in other species and contexts, scientific literature regarding wild boar carcass localisation in ASF-affected areas is scarce. ASF-infected wild boar (WB) carcasses are mostly found in cool, moist habitats (Morelle et al., 2019), demonstrating the challenges involved in detecting carcasses in real field conditions.

The efficacy of wild boar carcass detection fieldwork protocols would benefit from harmonised guidance based on the experience of different administrations and taking into account the variability of determining factors. However, there is a significant lack of robust scientific data to inform best practices for detection rates in diverse European scenarios (e.g. habitats, terrain and weather conditions). Accessible real-world operational data is limited and is often confined to unpublished reports. For example, there are reports documenting the deployment of dog-handler teams in Schleswig-Holstein during the 2020 ASF outbreaks (Karsten and Orłowski,

2020; Niemann, 2020, 2021). Even in countries where carcass searches with dogs are well established, significant differences exist due to administrative responsibilities and varying approaches resulting from federal structures. A comprehensive analysis of the strengths and weaknesses of different detection strategies, alongside their performance across varying environmental conditions, is essential. Evidence-based guidance on ASF carcass detection in Europe could help optimise detection strategies, for example by providing a decision matrix that matches the characteristics of a given local scenario with the most effective detection method or combination of methods.

The initial search can be focused on areas where there is a high likelihood of finding wild boar carcasses (e.g. based on their preferred deathbed locations) to enhance the efficiency of early detection and carcass removal. This will help with:

- Identifying high-risk zones for ASF outbreaks for further surveillance, their size, shape, extension, ecological corridors and possible barriers to wild boar and disease spread
- Establishing control measures (e.g., restrictions to movement) in ASF-affected areas
- Optimize resource allocation for carcass searches, and assessing feasibility of deploying specialized carcass detection units for ASF management

Among the active detection methods and techniques to find WB carcasses, we can identify:

- Ground Surveys: systematic searches by teams on foot or using vehicles (the latter, often risk-driven, e.g., water points)
- Trained dogs: use of specially trained dogs to locate carcasses by scent
- Drones/ unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs): use of UAVs to cover large areas quickly
- Their combinations

Passive (enhanced) detection of wild boar carcasses may involve public reporting and the involvement of hunters, encouraging members of the public to report sightings of carcasses and use mobile applications to report and track their locations. The latter can also be used for active, organised searches.

Ground surveys by humans

Deploying teams of trained personnel is a fundamental strategy for searching for and removing wild boar carcasses in order to control ASF.

Active surveillance consists of teams systematically patrolling designated areas on foot to locate and mark the location of carcasses. Specialised teams are then responsible for the safe collection and disposal of the carcasses.

Patrolling by car in areas where wild boar are known to be active and/or where they are likely to die (risk-based surveillance), performed by teams with sound knowledge of the terrain, is an effective way to quickly identify and manage carcasses.

Trained Dogs: the use of specially trained dogs to locate carcasses by scent

The use of specially trained dogs to search for carcasses can be employed for carcass detection, even in environments with dense vegetation (Barrientos et al., 2018; Dahlgren et al., 2012; Domínguez del Valle et al., 2020; Homan et al., 2001; Mathews et al., 2013). For example, detection dogs have been used to locate chamois (*Rupicapra pyrenaica*) carcasses during a sarcoptic outbreak (Alasaad et al., 2012). Working groups also use dogs to detect animals infected with diseases (<https://wd4c.org/our-work/biosecurity-invasives>) and humans infected with diseases such as SARS-CoV-2 (see the Federal Government of Germany, 2020; Grandjean et al., 2020; Jendryn et al., 2020). During the transition from the ASF control-and-prevention phase to the ASF eradication-and-control phase (Guberti et al., 2019), dogs can be utilised for the following:

- a) Controlling or reducing the wild boar population (e.g., searching for and chasing game at driven hunts or searching for wounded individuals).
- b) Detecting carcasses (whether found by chance or as part of systematic surveys).

c) Detecting ASF-infected meat or meat products. In some ASF-affected areas, such as those in Germany, detection dogs are already being used for carcass searches in field operations. Drones/ unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs): use of UAVs to cover large areas quickly Integrating drone technology into the surveillance and control of ASF has proven valuable, particularly for detecting wild boar carcasses and assessing key areas of wild boar activity. Drones equipped with thermal imaging cameras have been used to monitor wild boar populations, improving surveillance and containment efforts in hard-to-reach areas. They offer a rapid, efficient and safe way to detect wild boar carcasses, which helps to manage and control the disease effectively. This strategy complements other measures, such as intensive carcass searches and fencing to limit wild boar movement. The further integration of drone technology into wildlife surveillance represents a significant advancement in the fight against ASF and is a promising addition to the classical search for wild boar carcasses. As drone technology continues to evolve, its role in wildlife disease management is likely to grow, providing more efficient and safer methods of monitoring and controlling wildlife populations. Proper disposal is crucial in order to prevent the virus from persisting in the environment and infecting other animals. Until laboratory testing confirms otherwise, each carcass must be treated as potentially infected by ASFV. Regardless of how the carcass is detected, personnel must adhere to strict biosecurity protocols to avoid spreading the virus when handling and disposing of it. This includes wearing the correct protective clothing and decontaminating tools and vehicles. If detection dogs are being used, biosecurity measures must also be considered, including decontamination procedures such as showering and rinsing the dog's fur.

1.3. Wild boar carcass dating

A wild boar carcass found in a field is usually reported to the relevant veterinary authorities by staff involved in active surveillance programmes, or by hunters and other members of the public as part of non-targeted passive surveillance. These carcasses can be found in various states of decomposition, ranging from fresh to advanced, depending on the post-mortem interval (PMI, the time since death) and several intrinsic and extrinsic factors. In areas affected by or at high risk of ASF, it is key to quickly and accurately estimate the PMI. This estimation provides insights into the potential date of ASF introduction, which is crucial for informing disease control strategies, such as determining the extent of restriction zones. Due to the complexity of the decomposition process and the factors that influence it, accurate PMI estimation requires detailed on-site recording. This data can later be combined with other information to enable qualified personnel to estimate the most probable PMI and establish a range for its minimum and maximum values. Generally, the longer the PMI, the wider the range of the estimate (it is rarely possible to accurately determine the date of death of animals based on skeletal remains).

PMI estimation is affected by multiple post-mortem changes based on diverse methods. These changes are:

- Physical processes, such as body cooling and hypostasis (Palmiere et al., 2014);
- Metabolic processes, such as supravital reactions (Maeda et al., 2011);
- Autolytic processes, such as loss of selective membrane permeability and diffusion (Madae, 2005);
- Histochemical processes, such as rigor mortis (Khartade et al., 2017);
- Bacterial processes, such as putrefaction (Speruda et al., 2022).

The rate of carcass decomposition is affected by a multitude of variables, many of which are context-specific and poorly understood. Critical determinants of decomposition include intrinsic factors such as body size and weight, and extrinsic factors such as insects, large scavengers,

and weather conditions. For example, with increasing temperatures, the metabolism of microbes and insects increases, speeding up the decomposition process (e.g. Johnson et al., 2013; Pechal et al., 2013; Pechal, Benbow et al., 2014). Other extrinsic factors include microhabitat, such as sunlight, moisture, and soil type. For example, it has been suggested that wild boar infected with ASF often select cool, moist habitats as deathbeds. In a controlled experiment involving wild boar carcasses placed in cages to prevent access by scavenging birds and animals, advanced decomposition and skeletonisation were observed between 3–44 and 11–433 days post-mortem, respectively. However, one carcass did not reach skeletonisation even after two years. Carcasses exposed to sunlight decomposed more quickly than those in shaded areas, while standing water around the carcass slowed down the decay process (Probst et al., 2020). In a field study in which scavenging birds and animals had access to the carcasses, complete skeletonisation occurred within 4 days for a young female in summer and within 3 months for an adult male boar in a wallow during winter (Probst et al., 2017). In summary, the time it takes for carcasses to decay in nature varies widely and the above factors must be considered when estimating the time of death of animals found dead. Statistical models that represent the temporal dynamics of the number of carcasses attributable to ASF infection in affected areas highlight seasonal fluctuations in carcass numbers in the environment. These fluctuations reflect seasonal changes in carcass decomposition due to factors such as temperature (EFSA, 2021). The models consider that a substantial number of animals may die due to ASF shortly before viral fade-out. Predictions indicate that the ratio of virus-positive pigs that are alive to the number of carcasses attributable to ASF infection is always greater than 1:5 (Lange et al., 2021), suggesting the greater usefulness of intensive carcass collection in informing a potential decision related with disease freedom.

Previous epidemiological analyses using EFSA templates for data collection included the variable 'Degree of Decomposition of carcasses' as compulsory, indicating: 1 = fresh; 2 = decomposed; 3 = bones (EFSA, 2018). Standard approaches to determining time of death rely on techniques such as measuring body temperature, evaluating rigor mortis, assessing decomposition, conducting histopathological analyses, carrying out entomological studies and analysing environmental and associated evidence. However, accurate PMI estimation is complicated by the fact that the decomposition process is influenced by numerous factors, including climate, weather, body structure, cause of death, the scavenging community (vertebrate and invertebrate) and insect activity, as well as geographical location. For instance, Probst et al. (2020), demonstrates the importance of adapting PMI estimation methods to the species and their environments after addressing the variability of decomposition in wild boar and the influence of microhabitats. Accurate PMI estimation helps track the spread of ASF by providing insights into when and where infections occurred.

The main approaches to determine PMI include:

- Descriptions of body condition/decomposition stage assessment: Methods involving descriptions of body condition have an important subjective element. To estimate post-mortem interval (PMI), researchers have adapted a total body scoring system originally developed for humans. This system considers various stages of decomposition and environmental factors, providing a reliable PMI estimation through the use of standardised scoring systems that quantify decomposition.
- Entomology: the growth rate and stages of colonising insects can provide critical information about PMI. During the first few weeks, and during the active period of insects (normally spring to early autumn in the Northern Hemisphere), forensic entomologists estimate the age of the oldest necrophagous insects on the carcass or analyse succession patterns (Huffman & Wallace, 2011). This involves analysing insect

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activity, particularly the presence and development of flies and beetles, and estimating the age of insect larvae in order to determine the time of colonisation. This requires comprehensive knowledge of the local species composition, seasonal succession patterns, and development times.

- Environmental data: collecting and analysing temperature, humidity and other environmental data. Accumulated degree days (ADD) can be used to estimate decomposition rates. This complements other methods.
- Forensic histopathology involves examining different organs to improve post-mortem interval (PMI) estimation.
- Molecular techniques: PCR and qPCR analyse genetic material from cadavers to correlate with post-mortem interval (PMI).
- Spectrometry: techniques such as LC-MS and GC-MS analyse odorous amines and metabolites to determine post-mortem interval (PMI).
- Metabolomics/thanatometabolomics is the study of metabolites in biofluids and tissues. This field is particularly promising due to its affordability and quick analysis time. This emerging field analyses changes in metabolites in biofluids and tissues to provide a comprehensive understanding of post-mortem processes.
- Soil Analysis: analysing changes in soil composition beneath the carcass, which can indicate the duration of decomposition.

Combining multiple methods often provides the most reliable estimates. In most cases, PMI estimation in the early post-mortem period is likely to be based on gross changes, such as the quality of rigor mortis and the onset of decomposition, as well as early insect evidence. Likewise, PMI estimation in the late post-mortem period is likely to be based on entomology and gross changes, including the quality of rigor mortis and the stage of decomposition. However, these observations are highly variable and dependent on multiple factors. They should therefore be considered only as guidelines for very general estimation.

The main challenges in wildlife PMI estimation are:

- Environmental variability, including broad-scale variability such as climatic conditions and latitude, and small-scale variability such as soil composition, temperature, humidity, seasonality, sun versus shade and entomofauna.
- Species differences (e.g. standards derived from forensic studies on domestic pigs are not directly applicable to wild boar; Probst et al., 2020).
- Body mass differences
- Scavenger activity: wildlife carcasses are often subject to rapid scavenging, and scavenging activity varies by region and season.

2. Background and Terms of Reference

The contract entitled "Wildlife and One Health: wildlife ecology, health surveillance and interaction with livestock, human population, and environment (framework contract number: OC/EFSA/BIOHAW/2022/01) was awarded to the Universidad of Torino by EFSA. Further, we refer to this framework contract as an *ENETWILD* project. The specific objective 2 (SO2) of the framework contract refers to "Wildlife ecology, health surveillance and interaction with livestock, human population and environment".

WP 6 (ad-hoc scientific advice) of specific contract 2 indicates as terms of reference:

6.A) To provide a review of different methods to find wild boar carcasses in different countries, and the methods to date those carcasses, based on literature and field experience. This is addressed in the present report.

6.B) To propose protocols of use for each carcass detection system and carcass dating in different environments, how to adjust the effort depending on factors such as prevalence/seasons/etc. This is addressed in a further report.

Scope of the report

The report aims to review different methods to find wild boar carcasses in different countries, and the methods to date those carcasses considering different environments and considering the main factors determining their efficacy and practical application in the field (ToR 6.A).

3. Methods

The literature review considered a comprehensive range of sources, including published peer-reviewed articles, grey literature (such as technical reports and relevant websites), and direct insights gathered through semi-structured interviews with national-level experts involved in the management and prevention of ASF outbreaks in Europe. The inclusion of additional sources beyond published scientific literature was necessary due to the limited number and scope of peer-reviewed studies, which do not fully capture the evolving expertise and practical knowledge currently being developed and applied at the EU level. Grey literature and expert interviews provide essential, up-to-date insights from field experience and national management practices that are not yet reflected in the published scientific record.

3.1. Wild boar carcass search

Literature on wild boar carcass search

Figure 1 illustrates the general procedure, organization of work and steps performed to review literature on wild boar carcass search and their characterization by the consortium. The review of grey literature was based on using the same terms in general web browsers, as well as direct interviews to national administrations.

Literature review on methods to find wild boar carcasses in different countries

Figure 1. Procedure and steps performed to review the literature on wild boar carcass search. Our approach aimed at searching academic, peer-reviewed articles/documents describing wild boar carcass dating methods and protocols, their characterization and determining factors in:

- Biomedical databases (Medline)
- Science databases (Web of Science, Scopus)
- Two search strings we consecutively used. The first was:

((("wild boar") OR ("Feral pig") OR ("feral hog") OR ("feral swine")) AND (("carcass detection") OR ("carcass search") OR ("carcass removal") OR ("detecting carcasses") OR ("searching carcasses") OR ("finding carcasses") OR ("removing carcasses") OR ("locate wild boar carcasses") OR ("carcass location") OR ("wild boar carcasses") OR (deathbed) OR ("carcass detection dogs") OR ("collection of carcasses") OR ("Managing carcasses") OR ("found-death") OR ("dead wild boars"))

Additionally, in order to focus more specially and retrieve literature on drones as an approach to find wild boar carcasses, we used a second search sting as follows:

("wildlife") AND (("carcass detection") OR ("carcass search") OR ("carcass removal") OR ("detecting carcasses") OR ("searching carcasses") OR ("finding carcasses") OR ("removing carcasses") OR ("locate carcasses") OR ("carcass location") OR ("carcasses") OR (deathbed) OR ("collection of carcasses") OR ("Managing carcasses") OR ("found-death") OR ("dead wildlife")) AND ((drone) OR (UAV) OR (Unmanned))

Duplicates were removed. In addition to references retrieved directly from scientific browsers, we examined the literature cited to identify missing references and grey/technical literature (institutional literature/reports) and webs (using same search term in general browsers). Grey literature was search using the following national languages: Spanish, French, German, Italian, Polish, Czech, Swedish, Latvian, Estonian and Lithuanian. No time restrictions were applied to the inclusion of papers. All these references were managed in Zotero web library, and finally, collated in our data form.

3.1.1. Criteria for inclusion in the review

The criteria for inclusion in the review were:

- It deals with wild boar or relatives (e.g., feral pig) carcass search
- AND/OR provides relevant elements, not necessarily a protocol, that applies to wildlife carcass search in the field and could be applicable to wild boar, which fits our data collection models (see below).

Subsequent screening for exclusion prevented the use double entries (original articles can be part of reviews and/or grey literature).

3.1.2. Direct interviews

To complement the information obtained from the literature, address regional data gaps, and incorporate hands-on experience, additional data were collected by distributing the same standardized data collection form to national and local authorities or individual experts involved in active carcass search efforts. This was done in most cases through direct interviews to clarify doubtful points and enhance discussion. These efforts included both real-world scenarios and simulation exercises and were conducted by veterinary authorities, wildlife agencies, CVOs, and other relevant institutions which were, owing to their assigned duty, responsible for the coordination of wild boar carcasses search or directly involved in it.

3.1.3. The questionnaire and data form

A data form (excel form) was used to collect key information for characterizing wild boar carcass search activities. It was also used as a questionnaire/interview script for administrations. It is divided into two main parts (sheets):

www.efsa.europa.eu/publications

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- Description of the method/protocol to find wild boar carcass (Table 1).

If available, data on its application or surveys, which is useful to evaluate efficiency and determining factors (Table 2).

The data form was also used to guide direct interviews. Data was entered in the final database (Figure 1).

Table 1. First part (description of the method/protocol to find wild boar carcass) of the data form used to extract key information to characterize wild boar carcass search.

	ID Document
General	Name and brief description of the WB carcass search program/activities
	Country
	Region/province
	Brief description of typical landscape of the region where protocol is used (free text)
	Epidemiological scenario of application: 1) Infected area; 2) at the border with the infected area (< 10 km); 3) ASF free and intensive hunting areas
	Epidemiological scenario of application (II) 1) focal outbreak; 2) large front of disease
	Resources (protocol, report, paper) in the web (indicate web address)
	Main OBJECTIVES of program/report/protocol application (literally, summarize if long)
Organization	Administration body in charge: protocol development
	Administration body in charge: implementation
	Administration body in charge: data elaboration
THE PROTOCOL	Method/protocol: 1) Prospective patrols in sites favourable for dead WB presence; 2) Systematic combing of an area; 3) Dog detection, 4) Drones
	Brief description of the protocol (free text)
	ID Method (example provided)
	Criteria to select the searching zone/transect previous notifications of carcasses, proximity to risk (e.g., country borders, habitat connectivity), epidemiological models, random or regular within a given area, accessibility, etc
	When planning a search, do you pay special attention to environmental features present (e.g. mud, water holes, feeding grounds, fences, small rivers). Y/N
	In case of application of prospective patrols, detail the environmental features selected (e.g., mud, water holes, feeding grounds, fences, small rivers)
	WB carcasses dated? Y/N
	Concomitant use of drones? (Y/N)
	Effort: recommended team size (average or range)
	Effort: n° search events/day*team
	Effort: recommended area beaten per team*search event (ha)
	Effort: recommended area beaten per team*day (ha)
	Effort: length (km, average) search event
	Effort: length (km, average) day
Effort: average speed (km/h)	

	Effort: time (hours a day per team)
	Distance between people (m)
	Which is the metric used to estimate EFFICACY? (in WB carcass detection)
	Who supervises/leads each team? (e.g., a local forestry officer)
	Participant: veterinarian (Y/N/Optional)
	Participant: hunters (Y/N/Optional)
	Participant: forestry/rangers (Y/N/Optional)
	Participant: military (Y/N/Optional)
	Participant: farmers(Y/N/Optional)
	Participant: Fireguards (Y/N/Optional)
	Participant: Police (Y/N/Optional)
	Other government departments (indicate which)
	Other stakeholders (indicate which)
	Participant: dog handlers (Y/N/Optional)
	Nº trained dogs per team
	Nº untrained dogs per team
	Dog training: how long for, and specific target
	Dog breeds used
	Institutional or private body training the dogs
	Use of walkie-talkie by the team during search
	Financial compensation per field session? How much?
	Frequency a given area is screened
	Frequency team go to field (days)
	Specific form to be filled out and compiled after search session? (Y/N) Provide it
	WB carcasses position signalling method (GPS, GPS in smartphone and app like WhatsApp, visible tape, ...)
	Specific app developed to record, or trace or share field data. Indicate which
	Team trained on ASF biosecurity?
	Team trained on search protocol?
	First aid equipment available during search?
	Disinfection protocol included? (Biosecurity measures adopted before and after search)
	Disinfection equipment available during search?
	SPECIFIC awareness-raising and education campaign on Passive surveillance aimed at target stakeholders? Namely the importance of removing WB carcasses
Drone specific questions	Who operates drones?
	Thermal imaging used in drones
	Period of the day: 1) Any, 2) Diurnal, 3) nocturnal
	Type of drone: 1) multi-rotor, 2) fixed wing aircraft
	Drone model (and also camera model if external)
	Area (ha) beaten per flight
	Area (ha) beaten per day
	Height (altitude) of flight (indicate m, or if variable)

	Results are immediate or do collected images require further processing? How long?
	Automatized processing of images? Y/N, describe
	Search strategy (free text): indicating if systematic survey (pre-defined) or manually guided towards more risky or suspicious sites

Table 2. Second part (application or surveys to search wild boar carcasses in the field in order to evaluate efficiency and determining factors) of the data form used to extract key information to characterize wild boar carcass search. This part of the data form is linked to part 1 through the ID.

ID Document
ID method
Site
Habitat description (in view of visibility and accessibility characteristics)
Latitude
Longitude
Epidemiological scenario of application (I): 1) Infected area, 2) at the border with the infected area (> 7 km); 3) free and intensive hunting areas, 4) Drones
Epidemiological scenario of application (II): 1) focal outbreak vs 2) large front of disease
Main habitat type (EUNIS): Coastal habitats, wetlands, grasslands, heathlands and scrub, forests, sparsely vegetated habitats, farmlands
Habitat description: accessibility (rank accessibility of the searched area from 1 (lowest, absence of roads, deep slopes and cliffs, large areas of wetlands and associated vegetation) to 5 (highest, abundant roads, flat terrain))
Habitat description: visibility (rank visibility at 5m from 1 (lowest, totally covered by vegetation) to 5 (highest, almost no vegetation present))
Experimental study (Y/N)
Experimental objectives
Experimental group (indicate group)
Single search or aggregated data (single/aggregated). You can provide single search data in different rows, or aggregated in a single row
if aggregated data is reported, indicate duration (n° days) and n° of search events considered
Date (exact date or period, and duration of activities: total n° of days)
WB known or estimated density? Indicate (total or n° ind./km ²)
Obligate scavengers (vultures) present in the area (Y/N)
Surveillance effort as hours*person (per single event as n° people x n° hours, or total, measured by calculating the total number of field sessions, their duration, and the total

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human involvement in hours -duration of each field session multiplied by the number of people involved-
Effort: Actual team size (average or range)
Effort: n ^o search events/day*team
Effort: actual area beaten per team*search event (ha)
Effort: actual area beaten per team*day (ha)
Effort: actual length (km, average) of search event
Effort: actual length (km, average) day
Effort: actual average speed (km/h)
Effort: actual time (hours a day)
EFFICACY (specify metrics and unit)
Participant: veterinarian (N ^o per team)
Participant: hunters (N ^o per team)
Participant: forestry/rangers (N ^o per team)
Participant: military (N ^o per team)
Participant: farmers (N ^o per team)
Participant: Fireguards (N ^o per team)
Participant: Police (N ^o per team)
Other government departments (indicate which and n ^o)
Other stakeholders (indicate which and n ^o)
Participant: dog handlers (N ^o per team)
N ^o trained dogs per team
N ^o untrained dogs per team
Notes: anything regarding the search strategy and effort (free text)
Time since last search
Efficacy: number of carcasses collected
Efficacy: measure (description of metrics). E.g., by dividing the number of carcasses detected by the WB population
Estimated cost of search operations Euros/ha*day

3.2. Wild boar carcass dating

3.2.1. Literature on wild boar carcass dating

Figure 2 illustrates the general procedure, organization of work and steps performed to review literature on wild boar carcass dating by the consortium. Similarly to wild boar carcass search, the review of grey literature was based on using the same terms in general web browsers, as well as direct interviews to national administrations.

Literature review on methods to date wild boar carcasses in different countries

Figure 2. Procedure and steps performed to review the literature to review literature on wild boar carcass dating.

Our approach aimed at searching academic, peer-reviewed articles/documents describing wild boar carcass search methods and protocols, their characterization and determining factors in:

- Biomedical databases (Medline)
- Science databases (ISI Web of Science, Scopus)

We used the following sting:

("postmortem* interval" AND "wildlife") OR ("wild boar carcass" AND "dating") OR ("postmortem interval" AND "wildlife") OR ("postmortem interval" AND "wild boar") OR ("wild boar carcass" AND "decay") OR ("wildlife carcass" AND "decay") OR ("wildlife carcass" AND "dating")

(*) also used as "post-mortem" and "post mortem"

Duplicates were removed. In addition to references retrieved directly from scientific browsers, we examined the literature cited to identify missing references and grey/technical literature (institutional literature/reports) and webs (using same search term in general browsers), and all these references were managed in Zotero web library, and finally, target information was collated in our data form.

As done for the previous search, we also involved direct interviews with authorities (usually veterinary authorities) who had hands-on experience on the topic, (i.e., performed wild boar carcass dating during WSF outbreaks), to gather basic information on availability of carcass dating protocols as well as to identify additional grey literature and expert's insights. Grey literature was search using the following national languages: Spanish, French, German, Italian,

Polish, Czech, Swedish, Latvian, Estonian and Lithuanian. No time restrictions were applied to the inclusion of papers. To complement literature review, veterinary services, and the European networks of wildlife veterinarians (such as the EWDA Wildlife Health Network) were contacted to be eventually interviewed.

The criteria for inclusion in the review studies were:

- It deals with wild boar or related species (e.g., feral pig) carcass search
- AND/OR provides relevant elements, not necessarily a protocol, for improving wildlife carcass in the field (therefore applicable to wild boar), which fits our data collection models (see below). This includes factors that may determine wildlife (medium to big size) carcass search in the field.

Subsequent screening for exclusion prevented the use double entries (original articles can be part of reviews and/or grey literature).

3.3. The questionnaire and data form

Information from the questionnaire and the literature review was compiled through ad-hoc data collection forms. Table 3 shows this questionnaire.

Table 3. Data extraction form used for the analysis of literature sources and interviews

Geographical region where the study was carried out (i.e., country + bioregion)
Which type of carcass dating protocol is evaluated in the paper?
Original
Reproduced
Adapted
If it was reproduced or adapted, from which protocol was it adapted? Please provide APA reference is available
If it was adapted, what was changed from the original protocol?
Which tools were implemented in the protocol?
Metabolomics
Insect communities' evaluation
Macroscopic analysis
Camera trap monitoring for macroscopic analysis
Histology
Protein degradation analysis
Other:
Which other parameters were considered for assessing the dating protocol?
Environment/habitat/vegetation
Different geographical areas
Soil
Body part interested
Sun/shade
Age class
Sex
Body mass
Animal species
Duration of the study
Season for carcass initial deployment
Consumption by scavengers
Other:
What is the dating resolution?
Can this protocol be applied to different conditions?
Yes to different seasons
Yes to different species
Yes to different bioclimatic areas

No
The paper does not specify
Other
Factors that may favour or impair the dating process.
Has the protocol been validated (e.g., with WB carcasses of known date of death)?
If the protocol is not published as an indexed paper, but can be shared (even if not written in English), please provide web link and/or send to us by email

A data form (in Microsoft Excel format) was used to extract key information to characterize wild boar carcass search obtained through the literature research and questionnaires (Table 4).

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Table 4. Data form (excel form) was used to extract key information to characterize wild boar carcass dating obtained through the literature research and questionnaires.

ID Document	
General	Name and/or brief description of the WB dating protocol
	Country
	Region/province
	Resources (protocol, report, paper) in the web (indicate web address)
Organization	Administration body applying the protocol
Type of study/protocol	1) Protocol applied under controlled scenario (known PMI) 2) Protocol applied in the field (known PMI) 3) Application of protocol in real circumstances (unknown PMI)
Species	1) Wild boar 2) Other spp. but relevant to wild boar cases (detail why)
Indicate THE PROTOCOL	Method/protocol: 1) Metabolomics 2) Entomofauna' evaluation 3) Macroscopic analysis 4) Camera trap monitoring for macroscopic analysis 5) Histology 6) Chemistry (incl. protein degradation analysis) 7) Genetics 8) Other (specify):
	Which type of carcass dating protocol is evaluated in the paper? 1) Original 2) Reproduced 3) Adapted
	If it was adapted, what was changed from the original protocol?
	Brief description of the protocol (free text)
	For macroscopic analysis, indicate categories (stages) and their characteristics
	If used, describe (indicate cite) decomposition body score used
	Which other parameters were considered for assessing the dating protocol?
	Environment/habitat/vegetation Temperature and DDA indexes Different geographical areas Soil Body part interested Sun/shade Age class Sex Body mass Animal species Duration of the study Season for carcass `initial deployment Consumption by scavengers Other:
	What is the dating resolution?

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	Can this protocol be applied to different conditions?
	Yes to different seasons
	Yes to different species
	Yes to different bioclimatic areas
	No
	The paper does not specify
	Other
	Factors that may favour or impair the dating process
	Has the protocol been validated (e.g., with WB carcasses of known date of death)?
Applicability to real conditions (considering rapid assessment, if possible, in the field, can be needed)	
Precision for PMI estimation	
Available data form for applying the methods (indicate source and incorporate as an annex)	

4. Results

4.1. Wild boar carcass search

4.1.1. Available data

Overall, 95 items were identified as potentially including information relevant to describing carcass search methods and protocols, their characterisation, and the factors that may impact the findability of such carcasses (see Figure 4 for a description of the procedure and steps performed to review the literature on wild boar carcass search). Sixty of these 95 items included a description (more or less detailed) of methods for searching for wild boar carcasses (see Annex 1): 1) prospective patrols in areas favourable for dead wild boars; 2) systematic combing/screening of an area; 3) dog detection; and 4) the use of drones. The majority of the items corresponded to indexed research articles ($n = 29$) and interviews ($n = 22$), while grey literature (usually in the form of blogs, technical reports and unpublished presentations) and questionnaires/interviews were less well represented (see Figure 4, left). As expected, the majority of items originated from ASF-affected countries in Europe, namely Germany, Italy, Poland and Sweden. Relevant information was also collected to a lesser extent outside Europe, particularly in South Korea and other South-East Asian countries (see Figure 4 on the right).

Figure 4. Left: Type of literature: research article ((n=29), interviews (n=22), blog or grey (n=9) and questionnaires (n=3). Right: country of origin of the analysed items

Next, we provide a detailed description of the information obtained from these 60 items. The Figure 5, left displays the collected items on wild boar carcass search methods and protocols, which mostly occurred in ASF infected areas or at their border (<10 km), and to a lesser degree, in ASF free areas. Concerning spatial considerations, we found a similar number of items for focal outbreaks and for large fronts of ASF progression (or both) (Figure 5, right).

Figure 5. Left: collected items on wild boar carcass search methods and protocols Right: the epidemiological context referred equally to focal outbreaks and to large fronts of ASF progression (or both).

The wild boar carcass search protocols were mainly developed, implemented, and analysed by the respective veterinary services (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Frequency (n) of participation of different administrations and stakeholders over the steps of wild boar carcass search programs (a. development, b. implementation, and data analysis).

4.1.2. General descriptors of method/protocols to find wild boar carcasses

The methods to search wild boar (Figure 7) were classified as 1) prospective patrols (either on foot or by vehicle) in locations favourable for the presence of dead wild boars; 2) systematic combing of an area; 3) use of detection dogs; and 4) use of drones, as well as different combinations of them, and particularly the last three types, were the most commonly reported, with similar levels of representation.

Figure 7. Frequency (n) of methods to search wild boar in our sample (total n=60).

The criteria used to select the area in which to search for wild boar carcasses (Figure 8) were the likelihood of wild boar presence, proximity to risk (e.g. the border with other countries affected by ASF) and previous notification of wild boar mortality. To a lesser extent, the choice was determined by epidemiological aspects (such as risk models) and terrain accessibility. In certain cases, the need of train dogs under real circumstances was also a relevant factor.

Figure 8. Frequency (n=60 literature items) of predominant criteria to select the area to perform wild boar carcass.

The average team size (considering all different types of methods) is shown in Figure 9 (left), indicating that teams below 10 people (mainly between 3 and 8) predominated. In several cases (not shown) the answer was "maximum possible" but no specific indications were provided. In most cases, one single carcass search event is organized per day, and the

maximal number is 3 (Figure 9 right).

Figure 9. Left: Average team size considering all different types of methods (n=18). Right: number of wild boar carcass search events practiced by team*day.

The area covered during each wild boar carcass search event (Figure 10, left), which closely matched the area surveyed per day (Figure 10, right), as typically one search event was conducted daily, showed considerable variability. The surveyed areas ranged from 6 to 750 hectares, with a typical (modal) value of approximately 100 hectares.

Figure 10. Area surveyed per wild boar carcass search event (left) and per day (right), which were largely similar as typically one search event was conducted each day.

Only a few values were available for the distance travelled per event ($n = 4$), ranging from 1 to 6 km (2 to 6 km when considering distance travelled per event, $n = 4$). Average speed values were reported in four cases and ranged from 0.25 to 5.30 km/h, with the latter figure corresponding to dogs. The average number of hours spent searching for wild boar carcasses in the field per day was 4 (the typical value), ranging from 3 to 5 hours per day.

As indicated in Figure 11, the way in which the performance of wild boar searches was quantified was very variable. This result highlights the difficulty of comparing studies, experiences and methods. While an experimental study could compare the number of carcasses found relative to those hidden, in real scenarios the number of carcasses was usually unknown. In some cases, however, a number could be predicted based on modelling. Performance can also be estimated relative to the wild boar population, but population estimates are usually unreliable and do not account for the specific local impact of mortality.

Figure 11. Frequency of the way to quantify the performance of wild boar search over analysed cases.

Figure 12 shows the frequency of the responsible persons. Veterinarians were in charge of organisations searching for wild boar carcasses in the field, followed by officers from the hunting, forestry or park departments. To a lesser extent, hunters and professional dog trainers were also involved. Figure 13 shows the relative contribution of different stakeholders in terms of their presence in wild boar carcass search field teams. Hunters and dog handlers (who are often also hunters) were the most represented groups, accounting for around 75% of search events. They were followed by vets and forestry rangers (in around 50% of cases) and, to a lesser extent, by the army and the police. Other groups were present in a much lower number of cases (e.g. civil protection, farmers, hired staff, fireguards or firefighters).

Figure 12. Frequency of responsible persons for wild boar carcass searching events.

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Figure 13. Relative (%) presence of different stakeholders in wild boar carcass search field teams. N: absent, Y: present, O: optional (n=30). When present (in more than 50% of cases, n=30), the total number of dogs per team mostly ranged between one and two (Figure 14 top -1), with a maximum of 9, and they were mostly trained dogs (bottom -2). The total number of trained dogs per team (bottom left - 2A) presented a similar pattern, whereas untrained dogs were less frequently present and at lower numbers (one dog per team, bottom right - 2B).

Figure 14. Frequencies of the total number of dogs per team (top), total number of trained dogs per team (centre), and total number of untrained dogs per team (bottom) (n=30). Dogs were primarily trained by private organizations, and to a lesser extent, associations (scent dog breeders) and the administration (Figure 15).

Figure 15. Organizations responsible for training the dogs (%). Figure 16 (left) shows the frequency a given area is screened in our sample. While only for some methods the selected areas are surveyed once, normally, wild boar carcass search areas are screened every 2 weeks, which can extend to every 6 months in some cases. The frequency (how often, assuming certain regularity) teams go to wild boar carcass search activities was variable, in the majority of cases daily or weekly.

Figure 16. Organizations responsible for training the dogs (%). Dogs were primarily trained by private organizations, and to a lesser extent, by associations (such as scent dog breeders) and the administration.

The way the information on wild boar carcass presence and geolocation is collected and communicated is normally through GPS (Figure 17), which can be incorporated to mobile texting apps (n=20) or national/regional wild boar carcass collection specific ones.

Figure 17. The way information on wild boar carcass presence and geolocation (frequency in our sample) is collected and communicated (n=20).

In most cases, the field teams received training on biosecurity and disinfection, and were equipped with disinfection stuff (Figure 18, n=25). However, approx. 50% of protocols did not provide the field teams with the first aid equipment (we do not distinguish ASF confirmed and free areas).

Figure 18. Frequency of cases in which the field teams received training on biosecurity (top left) and disinfection (bottom left, n=25), and were equipped with disinfection stuff (bottom right). Provision of the field teams with first aid equipment is indicated in the top right figure. Specifically regarding the use of drones to detect wild boar carcasses, most of the operators were private in our reduced sample (see Figure 19 on the left). The investigation revealed no significant preference for the time of day to operate drones, with diurnal flights being favoured over nocturnal ones (Figure 19, right). All of the operators used thermal imaging to detect wild boar carcasses. Based on a reduced sample size (n = 6), the area screened per day presented a wide variation in size (from 10 ha in experimental studies to 500 ha in real cases), averaging 218 ha overall (70.6 SE).

Figure 19. Regarding the use of drones, most of the operators were private in our reduced sample (left). The preferred period of the day to fly drones was any (1), followed by diurnal flights (2), and to a lesser extent, nocturnal (3) and nocturnal combined with diurnal (2/3) (right).

4.1.3. Specific characteristics of different method/protocols to find wild boar carcasses

When we visualized the application of different methods in different countries (attending to those with higher representation in our sample, Figure 20), we evidenced marked differences. When selecting the countries where most of the information was collected, we evidenced that the use of dogs and drones predominated in Germany, combing by foot in Poland, and different approaches were similarly present in our sample in Italy (predominating combing).

Figure 20. Visualization of the application of different methods in different countries (attending to those with higher representation in our sample).

Regarding the use of methods to search wild boar carcasses in infected versus border areas (Figure 21, left), we found that different approaches were used in infected areas. Notably, a combination of methods was used more frequently, whereas patrolling was used less frequently. In border areas, combing was the most frequently selected approach, followed by patrolling. Dogs and drones were used less frequently. In terms of the comparison between focal and large-front outbreaks (Figure 21, right), patrolling and combing were the most frequently selected options for large-front outbreaks. For focal outbreaks, patrolling was never selected alone (it may be combined with other methods), and carcass searches were based on other methods. These comparisons are also visualised as sector diagrams (Figure 22).

Figure 21. Application of different methods regarding the epidemiological scenario. The left figure regards the use of methods in the infected *versus* the border area (<10 km), whereas the right figure refers to the comparison of focal *versus* large front outbreaks.

Figure 22. The application of various methods across different countries is depicted through sector diagrams, which align with the epidemiological scenarios. The figure in the top left illustrates the methods used in areas with infections, while the top right figure pertains to border regions. In the bottom section, the diagrams display the application of methods in different countries, tailored to specific epidemiological contexts. The bottom left figure focuses on the methods employed during focal outbreaks, and the bottom right figure addresses the strategies used along extensive fronts of ASF outbreaks.

Out of a total of 19 responses, 15 were from financially compensated searchers. However, our sample size was too small to enable us to compare the efforts and performance of the search according to this variable. As an example, compensation ranged from 0 to 120 euros per person per day for ground teams, 500 euros per day for drone teams (which is probably within the lower range for drones) and 450 euros per day per dog plus 250 euros per day per handler-assistant for dog teams.

Figure 23 shows the frequency (n) of area (ha) screened in a day according to the method used to find wild boar carcasses. The central values for combing and drones were approximately 100 and 150–200 hectares, respectively, with significant variation. Details of the specific surveys for each method are provided in a further section.

Figure 23. Frequency (n) an area (ha) has been beaten in a day according to the method used to find wild boar carcasses.

4.1.4. Description of data collected on surveys for searching wild boar carcasses
 We collected 28 surveys in which detailed information on the application and results of wild boar carcass search methods and protocols was presented. These surveys were mainly indexed research and grey literature, with only one item being an interview (from Piedmont, Italy; the remaining interviews only provided the general data presented above) (Figure 24). These surveys were from eight countries and included ten different experiences, with one to six different surveys per experience (specific trials by method, with more or less aggregated data). Only two of the experiences presented different methods: one in Germany, which presented data on combing, dogs, and drones; and another in France (on the border with Belgium), which presented data on surveys using patrols, combing, and dogs separately.

Therefore, the available information is scarce, incomplete and unharmonised, which may prevent a more detailed description and assessment of methods and strategies. Nevertheless, it is valuable.

Figure 24. Type of publications.

The sampled surveys mainly originated from European countries which are or at certain time were ASF affected (and France, which is at the border of the outbreak in Belgium), but also South Korea was represented (Figure 26 left). In our sample of surveys, the most represented method was combing (Figure 26 right), followed by the use of dogs, drones, and to a lesser extent, patrolling.

Figure 25. Sampled surveys mainly originated from European countries which are or at certain time were ASF affected (and France), but also South Korea.

Some surveys provided estimates of wild boar density in the screened areas; however, these estimates were never based on reliable methods (see Figure 26, left). Figure 26 (right) shows the total number of wild boar carcasses retrieved as frequencies in our sample, indicating that high variability is not only the consequence of carcass abundance and retrieval efficacy, but also due to high spatio-temporal variability in the aggregation of data, ranging from single survey events to much longer periods over larger areas. Below, we provide surface statistics for comparison.

Figure 26. Left: country of sampled surveys. Right: method of sampled surveys
 About the epidemiological scenarios of ASF for the collected surveys (Figure 27 left), they mostly were applied in ASF infected areas and also in all the gradients from infected to bordering and free ASF areas. In third position, surveys were applied in areas bordering ASF infected zones. Regarding the focal or disseminated nature of the outbreak (Figure 27 right), the larger proportion of surveys in our sample corresponded to focal outbreaks, and a lower proportion to large outbreaks.

Figure 27. Number of surveys according to the epidemiological scenarios of ASF. Left: ASF infected versus border areas. Right: focal *versus* disseminated (large front) outbreaks.

Figure 28 presents different indicators of the effort applied to find wild boar carcasses. Figure 28 (top left) shows the frequencies of the average number of people in teams participating in surveys (average per event), indicating that they mostly ranged from five to ten people. The area screened by each team per day also varied widely, from a few hectares to almost 1,000 hectares, with most values falling within the range of 100–200 hectares per team per day (top right). In terms of person per day, the screened surface area ranged from a few hectares to 50 hectares, peaking in frequency at 15–20 hectares (second row, left). The travelled distance per day ranged up to 5.6 km/h, with the majority of values occurring between 2 and 3 km/h (second row, right). The average speed was mostly between 0.25 and 0.75 km/h, with some values above 1 km/h (bottom left). Daily dedication in terms of total hours mainly ranged between three and four hours (bottom right). All these indicators will be interpreted in relation to the method used below, which can be an important factor.

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Figure 28. This panel shows different indicators of the effort applied to find wild boar carcasses (frequencies of values in our sample). The frequencies of values of the average number of people in teams participating in surveys (average per event) (top left), the area screened per team (top right), area screened in terms of person per day (second row left), the travelled distance per day (second row right), the average speed (bottom left) and the total hours dedicated in a day (bottom right).

The use of dogs to detect wild boar carcasses was an effective complement to manual searching, and could also be used as the main method with trained dogs. When used (in six out of ten reported cases), the number of dog handlers per group was typically one or two (Figure 29, top left), as was the number of dogs (top right). In three of these six cases, the dogs were specifically trained and relied on for the detection of wild boar carcasses rather than the team of people. Overall, the number of carcasses detected per km² mostly ranged from zero to four (bottom left). The ratio of retrieved carcasses to the estimated wild boar population in the area varied widely, from close to 0% to over 60% (bottom right).

Figure 29. This figure presents the frequencies in our sample of number of dog handlers per team (top left) as well as the number of dogs per team (top right), the number of carcasses

detected per screened surface (bottom left), and the proportion of carcasses retrieved to the estimated wild boar population in the area (bottom right).

4.1.5. Description of data collected on surveys for searching wild boar carcasses by different methods

In this section, we describe the data collected from a limited number of surveys on searching for wild boar carcasses, which may be relevant for characterising performance and logistical issues as a function of the applied method. Not all data were collected for all surveys and, specifically, for all methods of searching for wild boar carcasses. Figure 30 shows box plots of the area screened by a team per day, indicating that the total area screened may be smaller for combing than for dogs and drones.

Figure 30. Box plots of the screened surface (ha) by a team and day, as a function of the method.

The Figure 31 illustrates the travelled distance (km) per event and per day, respectively, by a team for different methods, evidencing that this distance tended to be lower for combing.

Figure 31. The travelled distance (km) per event (left) and per day (right) by teams of people participating in wild boar carcass search activities for different methods.

Figure 32 illustrates that even when the screened area and travelled distance seemed to be lower for combing, this approach also tends to require more dedication of people in terms of hours a day.

Figure 32. illustration of the dedication of people participating in wild boar search activities in terms of hours a day.

4.1.6. Identification of the main factors determining practical application of wild boar search methods in the field

We collected information on the main factors determining the applicability and performance of different wild boar carcass search, first, to identify them and secondly to determine their relative importance (in terms of the frequency these factors were reported over our survey). These factors are listed (1-18), and their frequency summarized (n=30) for all methods in Figure 33.

Figure 33. List of factors determining the applicability and performance of different wild boar carcass search methods and strategies reported over the collected surveys (N=30). They are ranked as a function of their frequency for all methods.

The factors that were more frequently reported are as follows:

- Knowledge on WB ecology, density, and spatial corridors
- Economic compensation
- Use of trained detection dogs
- Previous coordination of administrations and continuous monitoring/feedback
- Weather and season
- Visibility of carcasses: which is mainly determined by vegetation
- Use of complementary different methods

These factors are of a different nature. They may relate to wild boar ecology, the environment and climate, or to how the search is organised at different stages, including economic compensation for searchers and the means used, such as trained dogs and combined methods. Clearly, the relevance of these factors depends on the local scenario and the methods employed, even though their efficacy may diminish or increase under different circumstances. The next report will discuss the practical consideration of each factor in different scenarios and methods, providing guidance and practical recommendations for efficient wild boar carcass search programmes.

4.2. Wild boar carcass dating

4.2.1. Available data

A total of 48 documents were collected, including 43 research papers, three questionnaires, one book, one PhD thesis (which was not translated into the original publication). Two items of different nature (presentations) were also initially screened. Although eleven documents were selected for in-depth evaluation because they specifically addressed wild boar or described carcass dating methods later applied to wild boar, all identified references were screened in detail and assessed for potentially relevant information. Where applicable, data from these additional sources—covering other species (e.g., pigs, humans), wildlife in general, or the use of post-mortem interval (PMI) estimates in epidemiological models (e.g., EFSA reports)—were extracted using the data extraction form. This allowed for a more comprehensive understanding of the methods, even if these studies did not meet the initial inclusion criteria focused on wild boar. While data from these broader sources are not presented in this review, as the analysis was specifically targeted at wild boar, they remain available and could support future, species-specific or comparative analyses.

This approach reflects a pragmatic adjustment to the selection criteria, recognizing the limited availability of wild boar-specific studies and the relevance of transferable knowledge from other contexts.

The 11 selected references (see Annex 2) included 10 research papers and one questionnaire (provided by Dr Carlo Citterio regarding ongoing research). Three of these were developed in ASF-infected areas and the geographical distribution was mainly in Europe (see Figure 34), particularly in regions classified as Atlantic, Continental and Alpine (mainly Central Europe). However, similar, comparable studies originated from other temperate areas and were conducted in South Korea (n = 4). In two cases, dating referred to carcasses found in the Mediterranean area (Sardinia, Italy).

Figure 34. Geographical distribution of selected literature items (n=11).

Considering the references focusing on wild boar carcass dating specifically, four out of the 11 references were classified as experimental (Figure 35), which means that wild boar carcasses were experimentally deployed to evaluate the decay process, and PMI was known. On the other hand, in 7 cases the observations originated from field observations, and the exact PMI was unknown.

Figure 35. Frequency of selected references classified as experimental (wild boar carcasses were experimentally deployed and PMI was known) or field observations (the exact PMI was unknown).

Of the eleven references, two were original in that they developed their own methodology to determine PMI in wild boar carcasses (Figure 36). The remaining nine applied or adapted methodology that had already been described, using human or animal models. The described methodological approaches were most frequently based on the following original sources: Megyesi et al. (2005) in three cases, and combinations of different references in six cases: Brooks et al. (2018), Goff (2009) Anderson and Laerhoven (1996); Parsons (2009), Keough et al. (2009), Pittner et al., (2020) and Probst et al. (2020). The latter, in turn, relied on the adapted methodology of Megyesi et al. (2005). The adaptation involved the methodology and classification stages, but not the PMI values.

Figure 36. Frequency (n) of sources for wild boar carcass dating protocols over the selected references (n=11), as well as indication of the two ones that were original (n=11).

Figure 37 shows the frequency with which the different methods of wild boar carcass dating were applied by the selected references (n = 11). Direct morphological analysis of the decay/decomposition process, normally involving categorisation into different stages over time (see below), was the most frequently used method, either on its own or in combination with others (see Annex). This was often achieved using camera traps. Metabolomics, entomology and histology were used to a lesser extent in our sample. Metabolomics is defined as 'the discipline that provides comprehensive and systematic information on temporal changes in metabolite level profiles in biofluids and tissues, arising from the effects of the host genome, extended genomes, and other environmental or promoted factors' (Castillo-Peinado & Castro, 2016).

Figure 37. The frequency (number of studies) of different methods applied to wild boar carcass dating by the selected references (n=11). Several methods could be applied in the same studies.

Normally, one method was applied to date wild boar carcasses (most frequently macroscopic evaluation; six out of eleven cases). However, some applied three (two cases), four (one case) or five methods (one case) simultaneously to address carcass dating (Figure 38, left). For example, the morphological approach was sometimes coupled with histology. Furthermore, thermal imaging was implemented to assess the body temperature of the carcass. Based on macroscopic evidence, the different phases of decomposition were determined variably according to the study. Therefore, the number of decomposition categories used was also variable. Figure 38 (right) shows the frequencies of the number of categories throughout the process (not only at the early stages). The decomposition status was most frequently classified into four categories, which are well represented by the following terminology: fresh, bloated, active decay, advanced decay, dry remains and skeletal remains. In some cases, post-bloating occurred after bloating but before advanced decay, while in others, mummification occurred after dry remains. Some classifications also use a simpler distinction between early and advanced decomposition. Additionally, three studies evaluated the decomposition process using a methodology developed by Brooks et al. (2018), Megyesi et al. (2005) and Probst et al. (2020), who adapted it for wild boar.

Figure 38. Left: Frequency of the number of methods applied per study (n = 11). Right: Frequency of the number of categories used for the classification of the decomposition status after macroscopic evaluation all over the process (not only at early stages) (n = 8).

Of the various parameters described during the decomposition process, season and habitat/microhabitat conditions were the most frequently considered factors in the selected studies (Figure 39). Environmental temperature and the ADD score, which is related to the insolation and accumulated temperature hours to which the carcass has been exposed, were also frequently considered, as was the impact of scavengers on the carcass decay process. To a lesser extent, body size (or age as a proxy) was considered over the decomposition process. When analysing their relevance (not always these factors were considered relevant), the figure 39 (bottom) shows in frequency they were considered relevant in our sample (number of references out of 11).

Figure 39. Left: the frequency (n) of different parameters that were described during the decomposition/decay process in the wild boar carcass of the selected studies (n=11). Right: the factors that were considered as relevant over our sample in terms of frequency.

In general, such parameters affect the precision of PMI estimation, as winter, shade and humidity can slow the decomposition process and hinder correct estimation. Also, differences in skin structure between wild boar and pig can affect the evaluation. A series of factors have been identified as influencing PMI estimation. The most frequently mentioned factors were

temperature (high temperatures speed up decomposition), scavenger activity and environmental exposure (sun, shade, wind and moisture), which were mentioned six times. These were followed by seasonality and insect activity, which were mentioned five times (Figure 39 right). The other factors mentioned were humidity, body mass, species and carcass handling. For experimental studies, frozen carcasses or improper handling may influence the decay. Overall, geographical variability was also mentioned.

Figure 40. Resolution of the estimated PMI (n=10).

Figure 40 shows the results of the PMI estimation (n = 10). Quantification in terms of days was possible in experimental studies or those focusing on the early stages. However, in field observations where PMI provided estimations in terms of weeks or months, the accuracy and precision decreased with the progression of the decomposition. Generally, the accuracy and precision of the estimations decrease with the progression of the decomposition, meaning both the reliability of the estimation and the uncertainty of the time span (from days to months).

Regarding adaptability and applicability under varying conditions, the need for adaptation was frequently noted. These corresponded to factors influencing carcass decomposition, including species, seasonality, scavenger activity, temperature and environmental conditions. Overall, the importance of tailoring approaches to different bioclimatic zones and ASF-affected regions was emphasised. Additionally, the importance of establishing experimental reference settings under controlled conditions was highlighted, as was the need for proper training of operators and experts and the provision of specialised equipment and expertise.

5. Discussion

5.1. Wild boar carcass search

Eradicating ASF from wild boar populations is a complex process requiring a multifaceted approach. Detecting and removing wild boar carcasses in ASF-affected areas is key to improving the management of risk. The aim of this report is to review the methods used to locate wild boar carcasses and date them in different countries. This section focuses on descriptive aspects, paying attention to the main factors that may affect the efficacy and practical application of these methods in the field. A further report will provide guidance on using each carcass detection system and carcass dating method in different environments, offering a practical perspective for adapting them to specific scenarios.

Since ASF was last introduced in wild boar in Europe, two key developments have emerged: the continued spread of the disease to new areas, including new regions in Western Europe, and a better theoretical and empirical understanding of the most effective interventions for controlling the spread of ASF in different areas. However, this has not yet been sufficient to stop the spread of ASF beyond some successful and highly illustrative cases of focal outbreaks. Today, the disease remains challenging to eradicate from European wild boar populations, which are reaching unprecedented numbers and continuing to expand. This is due to ASF being transmissible by different routes, as well as the lack of a vaccine, among other factors.

5.1.1 The relevance of systematic and rapid response

In this context, the efficient detection and removal of wild boar carcasses in ASF-affected areas has been demonstrated to be key to improving risk management. This review shows that, 20 years after the last introduction of ASF in wild boar in Europe, the best methods and guidance for finding wild boar carcasses remain unharmonised and the information is difficult to access. There is also a lack of methodologies for locally adapted interventions according to scenario. For example, EFSA noted the need to develop protocols aimed at improving the search for wild boar carcasses as early as 2021. In the current context, the aim of this review is to identify accessible information. The data collected is valuable given its scarcity and the fact that it is diversified over many different sources and formats. It is generally incomplete and is normally described superficially, making it hard to harmonise and compare across geography, epidemiological situations and socioeconomic contexts. There is also a need to develop field trials to test the efficiency and precision of carcass search and dating, and to assess their adaptability to different scenarios. Actually, relevant research steps (mainly in central Europe) have recently been done in relation to the two issues evaluated in this review. These studies imperatively require further testing and adaptation over different biogeographical and epidemiological realities in Europe.

Regarding the initial steps to control the spread of the disease after the first cases of ASF were confirmed in wild boar, the Commission concluded that immediate action was essential to contain the disease, prevent its spread to domestic pigs and minimise economic damage. ASF is highly contagious and can spread through direct contact with infected animals or their secretions, as well as through contact with contaminated surfaces (such as carcasses). Infected wild boars contribute to its spread, but the effectiveness of removing carcasses depends on how quickly they are found and disposed of. Therefore, the response must be rapid, coordinated and science-based, following established disease control protocols. The immediate response and containment measures include establishing an infection zone (core

area and buffer zones) and banning wild boar hunting in the affected area. Passive carcass detection must be supplemented by active searches by professionals in hotspots identified by the competent authority, ensuring that they do not contribute to the spread of wild boar from this area. Alongside other measures (such as population control through hunting or trapping, fencing, and controlling contact between wild and domestic pigs), an intensive search for and removal of other wild boar carcasses in and around the infected zone must be carried out. Any measure that may increase carcass reporting should be incentivised (such as financial compensation), and strict biosecurity protocols must be followed for safe disposal. This is essential to identify the extent of the outbreak and remove potential sources of infection. An example of the usefulness of carcass finding in epidemiological studies of outbreaks was reported by Chenais et al. (2024), who described the situation in Sweden. However, despite the crucial importance of implementing the best possible measures at this stage and in subsequent stages, our review revealed that such protocols are conspicuously absent.

5.1.2 Current practices and knowledge gaps in carcass search methods

The lack of available protocols (or more generally, guidance) on searching for wild boar carcasses highlights the need to publicise and share local knowledge and experience of detecting wild boar carcasses. This is particularly important for large regions of Europe and for focal outbreaks of ASF. It also suggests that no systematic, planned searches for wild boar carcasses normally take place; rather, improvised searches occur variably in terms of design, methods and effort, even locally. Standardised data collection on the detailed characteristics of surveys and their performance (not necessarily their efficacy, which is a difficult parameter to estimate) is essential in order to learn lessons and help standardise this activity. Since the general principles of carcass disposal by wild boar and the methodologies that can be used are relatively well understood, it should be possible to adapt such protocols to different scenarios. However, no systematic attempt has yet been made to review the available information. Expertise in searching for wild boar carcasses should be tailored to Central and Southern Europe to enhance the search for infected carcasses, taking local factors into account. Additionally, some successful examples of systematic and well-organised carcass searches have emerged across Europe; Belgium is one such example. The detailed protocol implemented in Belgium to find wild boar carcasses and eliminate ASF has been shared, providing a breakdown of the routine and tools used to organise the searches. This protocol was later adopted as a model for action in Italy, which, after an initial fragmented approach, defined national guidelines for carcass search protocols to be implemented in different outbreak areas.

5.1.3 Carcass search strategies and key factors affecting efficiency

When discussing the data gathered from the surveys, which employed various methods to search for wild boar carcasses, it is important to note that only a limited number of surveys were used. These surveys may be significant in characterising the performance and logistical challenges associated with each method. Not all of the data that we aimed to collect was collected for all of the surveys (in fact, data on effort and efficiency was only available in

exceptional cases). Even when systematic protocols for carcass-searching procedures were not identified in the literature (either by teams of beaters, the use of dogs or drones), the low-detail descriptions of the strategies applied help provide valuable recommendations. In Europe, the majority of items originated from countries affected by ASF, namely Germany, Italy and Poland. The small sample size meant that it was not possible to make comparisons between countries or between scenarios, such as ASF-infected areas versus their borders or focal outbreaks versus large areas of ASF progression. Clearly, more information from more countries (ideally ASF-affected countries) is needed. When we requested information on the issue, a frequent answer from respective national veterinary administrations was that no systematic protocol for searching for wild boar carcasses exists. We advocate including detailed guidance on wild boar carcass searches as part of the wild boar population control and monitoring plans requested by the Commission from countries as part of the fight against ASF (Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2023/594 of 16 March 2023 laying down special disease control measures for African swine fever).

The criteria for selecting the area in which to search for wild boar carcasses that predominated among our sample were the likelihood of wild boar presence, proximity to risk (e.g. the border with other ASF-affected countries) and previous notification of wild boar mortality. All three of these priority criteria are related to an increased risk of finding dead wild boar, and of them being ASF-infected given the existing risk, once they are found. The reasons behind identifying priority areas for wild boar carcass searches may determine their shape and size, as well as the inspection strategies. Natural characteristics (e.g. forest distribution and abundance) and available information (e.g. first cases versus already-delimited infected areas) are useful for identifying areas. The choice between systematic spatial grids and habitat-driven approaches during inspection of risky sites (which are favourable as deathbeds) should be properly evaluated, even in light of patrolling by car versus systematic combing. The choice between habitat-based and grid-based search strategies can significantly impact efficiency. While habitat-based strategies are efficient as they target likely carcass locations, grid-based strategies prioritise thoroughness (Allepuz et al., 2022; Rogoll et al., 2024). The optimal approach often involves integrating both strategies to maximise effectiveness. A habitat-based strategy prioritises searching areas where wild boar carcasses are most likely to be found, based on ecological and behavioural knowledge. Factors considered include proximity to water sources, forest types, terrain and areas with minimal human disturbance. This approach is more efficient in terms of time and resources because searches are concentrated in areas where there is a high probability of finding carcasses, particularly in large or complex landscapes. However, it requires accurate habitat data and a good understanding of wild boar ecology, and it may miss carcasses located in less typical habitats. The grid-based strategy involves systematically searching a defined area by dividing it into a grid and searching each cell, thereby ensuring comprehensive coverage of the search area. This systematic approach reduces the risk of missing carcasses in less obvious locations, is relatively simple to implement and is effective in large areas. However, it can be very time-consuming and resource-intensive and is less adaptable to varying terrain and habitat types. In many real-world scenarios, a combination of both strategies is often the most effective. Habitat-based strategies can be employed to identify high-priority areas, after which grid-based searches can be conducted to ensure thorough coverage within those areas. This approach balances speed and coverage, reducing the likelihood of missed carcasses. Combining different methods, such as drones and canine units, can further enhance the efficiency of these approaches. In summary, habitat-based strategies are more efficient in targeted areas with known wild boar activity, while grid-based strategies provide comprehensive coverage and are useful in areas

where habitat data is limited. Therefore, the choice between habitat- and grid-based strategies depends on the specific goals and available resources.

A major constraint in developing carcass search strategies based on known experiences is that the performance of wild boar searches has rarely been quantified and, worse still, the methods and metrics used were not comparable. Another relevant limitation is the lack of comparisons between methods, particularly fair comparisons under similar circumstances.

A key area requiring guidance concerns the necessary efforts and resources to be deployed over time. The efforts applied could only be partially determined, and the lack of detailed information, as well as the use of different metrics, prevented comparisons between methods, strategies, areas and epidemiological scenarios. This also prevented the determination of real efficacy in terms of the proportion of carcasses found. Nevertheless, we have described different indicators of the effort applied to finding wild boar carcasses (as they are not harmonised and cannot be harmonised by us with the available information). As an indication, the average number of people per team participating in surveys was 5–10, and the area screened per team per day varied widely, with most values around 100–200 ha per team per day. In terms of person per day, the screened surface area ranged between 15 and 20 ha in most cases. The travelled distance per day was up to 5.6 km, most frequently between 2 and 3 km (second row, right). The average speed was mostly between 0.25 and 0.75 km/h, with some values above 1 km/h when dogs were used. Even when the area screened and the distance travelled seemed lower for combing, this approach normally required more people to be dedicated for longer periods of time. These parameters provide guidance on determining the required human effort, which will be considered in detail in the report providing recommendations.

We collected information on the main factors reported in the reviewed literature that may affect the suitability and effectiveness of different protocols for searching for wild boar carcasses. Considering these factors in the context of the reviewed literature can provide an indication of their overall importance. The factors reported most frequently in our sample were: 1) knowledge of wild boar ecology, density and spatial corridors; 2) economic compensation; 3) the use of trained sniffer dogs; 4) the coordination of administrations and continuous monitoring/feedback; 5) weather and season; 6) visibility of carcasses (mainly determined by vegetation); and 7) the complementary use of different search methods. These factors encompass natural variables linked to wild boar behaviour and environmental conditions, as well as operational aspects ranging from financial incentives to the strategic use of resources such as scent-detection dogs and methodological diversity. Clearly, the importance of each factor varies depending on the specific local context and the methodologies employed, as these can either enhance or reduce the effectiveness of the search protocols under different conditions. A separate report will discuss each factor in relation to various scenarios and techniques in more detail, offering practical guidance and recommendations. Surveillance and search techniques such as active ground searches by humans or aerial surveillance to reduce operator fatigue are far from 100% effective. While this review identified four methods for the active detection of wild boar carcasses, an integrated approach could improve the efficiency and coverage of surveillance efforts, particularly in hard-to-reach areas. Combining methods in an integrated approach may enhance efficiency, especially in inaccessible areas.

Ground survey teams may work alongside other surveillance tools, such as drones equipped with thermal imaging cameras and carcass-detection dogs. Patrolling known or possible hotspots for wild boar activity or death beds by car (risk-based surveillance) complements a more systematic search by teams of beaters, particularly for the initial, preliminary estimation of the infected area, in which more systematic search activities can then be developed. The

first 72 hours are critical for effective disease control, so patrolling appropriate areas and hotspots during this period is essential.

Using vehicles to patrol known and accessible hotspots is a relevant approach, particularly for rapidly delimiting the possible infected area and determining the priority areas in which to apply more systematic methods, such as combing the area with survey teams, dogs and drones. Effective patrolling requires an understanding of the relationship between wild boar selected deathbeds and ASF. Studies on the habitat preferences of wild boar affected by ASF have shown that they tend to seek out specific habitats and micro-sites for their 'deathbeds'. These preferences can aid targeted carcass searches and should also be considered in routine passive (enhanced) surveillance. Key findings (e.g. Morelle et al., 2016; Allepuz et al., 2022; Rogoll et al., 2024) indicate that a high percentage of ASF-positive carcasses are found in these preferred habitats:

- Forests and transitional zones between woodland and shrubland, particularly in younger forest stands. When in meadows, infected individuals prefer areas with a dense herb layer.
- Quiet and secluded areas: infected wild boars often avoid areas close to roads and forest edges, seeking undisturbed locations away from human activity.
- Cool, moist habitats and water sources: this behaviour is thought to be linked to the fever associated with ASF, as the animals seek relief in cooler, damp locations. Research has consistently shown a correlation between ASF-positive wild boar carcasses and proximity to water sources such as rivers and streams. This highlights the importance of including areas near water sources in ASF surveillance and carcass search efforts.

Patrolling known or possible hotspots for wild boar activity or death beds by car (risk-based surveillance) complements a more systematic search by teams of beaters, particularly for the initial estimation of the infected area, in which more systematic search activities can then be developed.

Finding wild boar carcasses by combing areas on foot involves good planning and coordination. Teams are organised and briefed on the specific areas to be searched. Maps and GPS data are often used to identify high-risk zones where wild boar are likely to be found, such as near bodies of water, forest edges and transitional zones between different types of vegetation. Teams typically consist of trained personnel, including veterinarians, hunters, foresters and volunteers. They must be equipped with protective gear to prevent the spread of the virus. The search is conducted in a grid pattern to ensure thorough coverage of the area or risk zone. Teams walk through the designated zones, carefully inspecting the ground and undergrowth for carcasses. Drones and other aerial surveillance tools can complement ground searches, especially in difficult-to-access areas.

Using trained dogs and drones should speed up detection. It is unlikely that any of the detection methods match the capabilities of dogs. However, as with any method, the use of dogs has certain disadvantages. For example, their operational capacity in the field is limited, and their ability to locate odours can vary greatly from one dog to another. Nevertheless, well-trained dogs remain the most portable and versatile scent detection tools currently available. Searches of carcasses conducted by handlers with specially trained dogs have proven effective, even in dense vegetation and when searching for small remains, such as single bones.

Appropriate biosecurity measures should also be considered when using detection dogs. Even when little literature is available, our review showed that integrating drone technology into ASF surveillance and control has proven valuable in detecting wild boar carcasses (Rietz et al., 2023). The further integration and generalisation of the use of drone technology in wildlife surveillance is promising and still unexploited, representing a significant advancement in the

fight against ASF. Drones equipped with thermal imaging cameras can monitor wild boar populations, enhancing surveillance and containment efforts in inaccessible or hard-to-reach areas. They have high potential for the rapid, efficient and safe detection of wild boar carcasses. This strategy complements other measures, such as intensive ground searches for carcasses. As drone technology continues to evolve, its role in wildlife disease management and specifically in the detection of wild boar carcasses is likely to expand in the near future. Out of a total of 19 responses, 15 were from financially compensated searchers. However, our sample size was too small to enable us to compare the efforts and performance of the searches according to this variable. For illustration purposes only, the range was €0–€120 per person per day for ground teams, €500 per day for drone teams (which is probably within the lower range for drones) and €450 per day per dog plus €250 per day per handler-assistant for dog teams. As group sizes vary, it is difficult to standardise metrics for comparison. Due to the very limited sample size, these values should not be regarded as fully representative. Financial compensation may significantly incentivise the search for and reporting of wild boar carcasses as part of ASF control efforts. This could enhance reporting and detection by encouraging hunters, foresters, landowners and the general public to actively search for and report wild boar carcasses. Searching for carcasses is time-consuming and labour-intensive, particularly in large or remote areas, but financial compensation provides a tangible incentive to motivate individuals to dedicate their time and effort to this task. It may also enhance surveillance effectiveness by increasing the number of people searching for carcasses, leading to a higher detection rate. Furthermore, financial compensation can be linked to adherence to biosecurity protocols, such as proper carcass handling and disposal. This ensures that carcass removal is conducted safely and effectively, thereby minimising the risk of viral spread. Furthermore, financial compensation can foster cooperation between different stakeholders, including government agencies, hunting associations, and local communities. By incentivising carcass removal, financial compensation contributes to the overall effort to contain ASF, the economic consequences of which for the pig industry can be devastating. Therefore, the compensation is seen as a preventive measure that is less expensive than the alternative. However, it is important to implement these measures carefully to avoid unintended consequences, such as providing an incentive to kill healthy animals for financial gain. One option is to base compensation models on a per-carcass bounty, whereby individuals receive a fixed payment for each reported and confirmed wild boar carcass. This approach is better suited to passive surveillance, which has significantly improved early detection rates in ASF-affected regions. Similar to the remuneration granted for wild boar hunting and monitoring efforts in some federal states in Germany and other European countries, governments have provided €50–€200 per carcass to encourage search efforts. However, it is better to support organised active search efforts by funding search teams (including hunters, forestry workers and trained personnel), hiring detection dog teams (which requires providing training resources) and financing drone and thermal imaging technology to efficiently locate carcasses.

5.1.4 Carcass handling, biosecurity, and the need for early removal

Carcass handling and biosecurity are essential to ensure that carcass removal contributes to lowering the risk of ASF spread, rather than increasing it. Once a carcass is found, it must be carefully documented and samples must be taken by professional veterinary staff for

laboratory analysis to confirm ASF. The carcass is then safely removed and disposed of according to biosecurity protocols. The area where the carcass was found must be disinfected to prevent the further spread of the virus. Equipment and personnel must also be disinfected after the search, with special care given to search dogs.

Studies suggest that quickly removing a high proportion of carcasses can significantly reduce the spread of the virus by breaking the cycle of infection, and this approach is most effective when implemented early in an outbreak. Epidemiological models provide theoretical values for the proportion of carcasses that need to be removed to effectively control and eradicate disease from wild boar populations. This proportion depends on specific circumstances, the application of other measures (e.g. population reduction) and the epidemic phase. However, the goal is always to remove as many infected carcasses as possible to prevent the virus from persisting in the environment. There is no universally agreed "proportion" of carcasses that must be found to guarantee eradication. Studies indicate that only a small percentage of wild boar carcasses are typically found in natural habitats. This makes eradication very difficult. Based on our review, a lack of data on specific surveys prevented us from evaluating the effectiveness of current approaches in detecting wild boar carcasses. More experimental trials and comparisons of different methods in terms of effectiveness and logistics are needed. In any case, the focus is on a comprehensive strategy that includes the effective removal of carcasses, with the aim of finding and safely removing as many as possible. Achieving 100% removal, or even approaching this proportion, is normally unrealistic unless focal outbreaks are detected in the early infection phase due to the challenges of searching large forested areas. There is no specific proportion of wild boar carcasses that must be found in order to eradicate ASF, and the exact percentage needed is context-dependent. However, continuous monitoring in affected areas is useful for determining the exit strategy, and carcass dating is also relevant for this purpose (see below). In summary, rather than focusing on a specific proportion, the emphasis is placed on maximising carcass removal in conjunction with other control measures.

5.1.5 Future research and experimental trials to improve search efficiency

As we saw above, determining the efficacy of wild boar carcass searches in the context of ASF control requires a combination of field methods. Key experimental areas need to be developed in order to gather reliable information on the most effective strategies. In terms of search methodologies and efficiency, comparative search experiments should be conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of various methods, such as human search teams versus canine search teams, systematic grid searches versus targeted searches based on habitat analysis, and the use of drones with thermal imaging versus traditional ground searches. Researchers would measure the time taken, the area covered and the number of carcasses found by each method. Any trial must be conducted in such a way that the results can be compared between zones using similar (or interchangeable) metrics. This will inform decisions on the most efficient and cost-effective search strategies in different circumstances and contexts. Experiments should also assess the impact of searcher experience, training and fatigue on carcass detection rates. This could involve controlled trials in which searchers with different levels of experience search simulated areas containing hidden carcasses. This approach could also be extended to dogs. Regarding detection probability, studies should aim to quantify the probability of detecting a carcass within a given area. This would involve placing known carcasses in the field and conducting repeated searches to determine the detection rate. Factors such as the stage of carcass decomposition, vegetation cover and terrain can be

varied. The best improvements to date have been made in relation to habitat preference and spatial analysis (literature). Several studies have analysed the spatial distribution of carcasses found in relation to environmental factors such as proximity to water sources, forest type and density, terrain, elevation and distance to roads and human settlements. This helps to identify areas where carcasses are most likely to be found. Spatial and epidemiological modelling can also predict the distribution of carcasses based on environmental variables or the expected number to be retrieved, depending on the epidemiological phase. This is important for efficiently allocating search resources and applying the exit strategy. Linked to the next point of discussion are studies analysing how quickly carcasses decompose in various habitats and how visible they are during the various stages of decomposition. This would help searchers know what to look for and where to look for carcasses. Finally, technology integration requires addressing drone technology specifically. The effectiveness of drones equipped with thermal imaging and high-resolution cameras for carcass detection can be evaluated by conducting field trials that compare drone-based searches with traditional ground searches. More specifically, studies are needed to optimise the use of trained dogs for carcass detection. This includes researching scent detection ranges, training protocols and the impact of environmental factors on canine performance. Table 5 below proposes some field experiments to determine the efficacy of wild boar carcass searches, which must be conducted in different areas and habitats across Europe where wild boars are found. Controlled experiments are needed to evaluate how effectively wild boar carcasses can be located in different conditions. These experiments should assess the efficiency of different search methods (human, canine, drone, etc.), environmental influences and detection success rates.

Table 5. Proposal of some field experiments to determine the efficacy of wild boar carcass searches over different scenarios of Europe.

<p>1. Controlled placement and recovery experiments Objective: Assess how different search methods perform in locating wild boar carcasses. Methodology: Place wild boar carcasses in various environments (forest, grassland, wetland). Use different search techniques: Human search teams (with and without tools like thermal imaging) Canine units trained for carcass detection Drones (thermal or multispectral imaging) Combinations Record detection rates, time taken, and environmental challenges. Expected Outcome: Identifies the most efficient search method under various conditions, which may help to make decision locally on best strategy</p>
<p>2. Impact of environmental conditions on detection Objective: Determine how weather, terrain, and vegetation affect search success. Methodology: Conduct searches in different seasons, weather conditions (rain, fog, snow) and terrain. Compare detection success in dense vs. open vegetation according to season and methods. Analyse also how the decomposition stage affects detection ease (fresh vs. advanced decay). This experiment can also be done for each method under different environments to evaluate how environmental conditions affect detection efficiency (for instance, for dogs, see below). Expected Outcome: Provides insights into optimal search conditions and limitations.</p>

<p>3. Effectiveness of drone-based searches for wild boar carcasses Objective: Evaluate drones for detecting wild boar carcasses compared to ground searches. Methodology: Test thermal imaging drones during day and night. Compare drone-detected vs. human-detected carcasses. Assess how altitude, flight speed, and sensor type affect detection, as well as decomposition status, and vegetation. Expected Outcome: Determines the viability of drones as a cost-effective alternative for large-scale carcass searches under specific conditions.</p>
<p>4. Evaluation of drone-based searches for wild boar carcasses: drone characteristics settings, development, and application of artificial intelligence models Objective: Evaluate best settings for drone-based detection, and development and validation of artificial intelligence models to automatize wild boar carcass detection Methodology: Experimental Design. 1. Selection of study Sites: Initially select one study area where define and test settings. Then, choose diverse landscapes and generate diverse images to train AI models. 2. Deployment of carcasses: Place wild boar carcasses (or synthetic carcass models) at varying distances, locations, covered by vegetation partially or not, different positions, within the study site and monitor over the decomposition process. Other species can be used to refine the AI model 3. Development of AI model 4. Validation with independent observations Equipment: Thermal imaging drones (detect heat differences, useful at night), multispectral drones (analyse vegetation changes due to decomposition), RGB optical drones (high-resolution visible light cameras) Expected Outcomes: To optimize the efficacy of searching for wild boar carcasses. Identify best settings and functionalities for drone search strategies and automatize the process of detection, which will allow developing planned flights without the need of manual identification, speeding up the process. Optimize drone flight paths, altitudes, and imaging settings for maximum efficiency.</p>
<p>5. Role of scavengers in carcass disappearance Objective: Measure how quickly scavengers remove carcasses, impacting search accuracy. Methodology: Place motion-activated cameras near carcasses to monitor scavenger activity. Compare detection success in areas with high vs. low scavenger populations. Expected Outcome: Helps estimate the time window for effective carcass search before removal.</p>

6. Forensic odour analysis for canine training

Objective: Improve canine search accuracy by identifying key decomposition odours.

Methodology:

Analyse gas emissions from decaying wild boar using gas chromatography.

Use results to refine canine training for improved scent recognition.

Expected Outcome: Enhances the reliability of scent-detection dogs for carcass searches.

Experiments with odour detection dogs for wild boar carcass searches

Using detection dogs to locate wild boar carcasses is a promising approach, but their effectiveness depends on scent training, environmental factors, and search methodologies.

Below are detailed experiments to assess and improve the efficacy of odour detection dogs in carcass searches.

7. Performance testing of trained dogs in different environments

Objective: Evaluate how environmental conditions affect canine detection efficiency.

Methodology:

Testing Locations: Conduct searches in dense forests, grasslands, wetlands, and mountainous areas.

Place carcasses at varying depths (surface vs. shallowly buried).

Time-Based Testing: Conduct trials at different decomposition stages.

Evaluate changes in detection success over time (0-48 hours, 1 week, 2 weeks, etc.).

Weather & Temperature Variations: Conduct searches under different weather conditions (rain, fog, snow, heat).

Measure scent dispersion and dog response under each condition.

Expected Outcome:

Determines optimal environments and conditions for search effectiveness.

Helps adjust training for difficult terrain/weather conditions.

5.2. Wild boar carcass dating

To our knowledge, no systematic attempt has been made to review the available information on dating wild boar carcasses. This review first evidenced that determining post-mortem interval (PMI) in wildlife carcasses, and in the case of wild boar in particular, is exceptionally difficult, presenting an even greater challenge than in human forensic cases. Secondly, aside from experimental studies (i.e. cases with known PMI), there is still a need to transfer and validate recent research experiences for the subsequent development of protocols and local application, given the lack of available adapted protocols/guidance on wild boar carcass dating for real-life cases. While known experiences from Central Europe can be adapted for use in other areas, local studies with similar methodology are required. Additionally, while the recent development of methods such as metabolomics-based approaches shows promise, it requires further development, as well as the appropriate facilities and expertise, to enable rapid assessment.

5.2.1 Overview of available studies and geographic distribution

A total of 48 documents were identified, most of which were research papers. However, only 11 of these were selected for a detailed evaluation of methods on carcass statistics, as they referred to wild boar and/or had developed carcass dating methods that were later adopted for wild boar. All references were screened in detail and relevant information that could be directly transferred to the evaluation of carcass dating methods in wild boar was considered, including references to other species (wildlife, pigs, humans) and references incorporating carcass post-mortem interval (PMI) estimations into epidemiological models. Only three of these eleven items were developed in ASF-infected areas, and the geographical distribution was mainly in Europe, with significant contributions from South Korea, where environmental conditions make the results transferable to Europe. Notably, four of the references were classified as experimental, meaning that wild boar carcasses were deployed for the purpose of evaluating the decay process and the post-mortem interval (PMI) was known. This is important for practical applications because it provides estimations of various parameters that can be determined or measured in wild boar carcasses over time and correlated with known PMI. Wild boar deaths in real ASF scenarios are often discovered late, with limited data on the immediate surrounding conditions at the time of death. This makes the application of common forensic entomology, pathology or temperature-based models difficult. The remaining seven cases originated from field observations and, although the exact PMI was unknown, they provided crucial information on the main circumstances and limitations to be addressed when dating wild boar cases in real scenarios.

5.2.2 Methodological approaches

The sources supporting different methodological approaches were not particularly diverse. Of the 11 references, two were original in that they developed their own methodology to determine post-mortem interval (PMI) in wild boar carcasses. The remaining studies applied or adapted methodology that had already been described using human or animal models. This indicates that 'classical' forensic techniques, which are mostly based on macroscopic and entomological evidence, can be easily transferred, but their application requires adaptation to wild boar carcasses as well as to prevailing environmental and ecological conditions. Notably, one of the original cases refers to the first application of metabolomics to wild boar carcasses, specifically direct analysis in real time using DART-MS (Zacometti et al., 2025). Further studies are needed to relate metabolites to PMI, but this technique has shown its potential, especially given the low cost of the analysis and the simplicity and speed of sample preparation and analysis.

Of the various methods employed for dating wild boar carcasses in the selected references, direct morphological examination of the decay/decomposition process was the most frequently used, either alone or in combination with other methods. This process typically involved categorising the carcass into different stages over time, which was not always entirely objective. Based on morphological evidence, the different phases of decomposition were determined variably according to the study. Examining visible stages of decomposition (e.g. fresh, bloated, active decay, advanced decay and skeletonisation) can provide clues about the time of death, although this method is less precise for wildlife due to the aforementioned unpredictable variables. The number of decomposition categories used also varied, with four categories being the most common. These categories can be represented by the following terminology: fresh, early decomposition, advanced decomposition and skeletonisation/mummification. This reveals variable categorisation and standards (flexible use

of original sources), but this methodology can be harmonised if standards align well with the main primary sources in the literature, or if standards are established. It is important to note that we are referring to decomposition stages based mostly on macroscopic evidence; however, these stages are not universally associated with specific post-mortem intervals (PMI), as this depends on the specific context and conditions. For instance, a large wild boar may experience a prolonged bloating stage due to gas build-up, whereas a smaller animal may progress through this stage more quickly. These differences in the stages of decomposition can affect the timeframes used to estimate PMI.

Three studies scored the decomposition process based on the methodology developed by Brooks et al. (2018), Megyesi et al. (2005) and Probst et al. (2020), the latter of which adapted the methodology for use with wild boar. This allows the use of a quantitative measure of decomposition to analyse the correspondence and account for the effects of the factors that determine carcass decay (i.e. predictive models of estimated post-mortem interval (PMI), see Müller et al. (2024)). Considering and analysing the effect of factors determining carcass decomposition/decay is therefore relevant. We found that different parameters were described in the selected literature on the decomposition process, with season and habitat/microhabitat conditions being the most frequently considered. Environmental temperature and the Accumulated Degree Days (ADD) score were also frequently considered, as was the impact of scavengers on the carcass decay process. The ADD score is a method used to estimate PMI by tracking carcass decomposition. This method relies on the accumulation of thermal energy over time, which is crucial for understanding the rate of decomposition. The ADD score is calculated by recording the previous daily average temperature. The maximum and minimum temperatures on the relevant days are recorded and the accumulation is determined over time. Daily degree days are then summed over the decomposition period to obtain the total ADD. This total reflects the cumulative thermal energy that has influenced the decomposition process. Using the ADD score enables researchers to standardise the decomposition process across different environments and conditions, facilitating comparison of results and more accurate estimation of PMI. To a lesser extent, body size (or age as a proxy) was parameterised throughout the decomposition process in the sampled studies.

Next, based on the findings of this review, we indicate the main considerations that need to be accounted for when determining the PMI in wild boar:

- There is extreme environmental variability. Wild boar exist in Europe in a variety of habitats, which exposes their carcasses to a wide range of conditions. Fluctuating temperatures, varying humidity levels and exposure to sunlight, shade or freezing conditions can all significantly impact decomposition rates. In some cases, the carcasses of wild animals may be partially preserved in cool, dry or submerged conditions, which can slow decomposition and make it harder to estimate post-mortem interval (PMI). This variability makes it nearly impossible to establish standardised decomposition timelines unless they are calibrated locally, and the time ranges determined will probably be wide, particularly as the decomposition process progresses. Interestingly, better precision can be obtained during the first months of PMI (based on experimental studies in Germany) (Probst et al., 2021; Rietz et al., 2023). An effective search strategy can facilitate access to carcasses at earlier stages and therefore PMI estimation can be an effective tool for determining the most recent infection event in the area. This is essential for the exit strategy, but as mentioned, requires implementing an efficient carcass search strategy. Characterising the age of the individual may provide clues as to the minimum PMI, given the seasonality of the species' births.

- Specific decomposition. For wild boar, relevant differences in body size influence decomposition processes: larger animals decompose more slowly than smaller ones. To a lesser extent, fur influences decomposition processes, depending on the season and attitude.

This species tends to develop abdominal adipocere (Forbes et al., 2005), a soft, white substance formed from fatty tissue in a decomposing body after death. It persists for a long time (even during skeletonization) and is difficult to date. Animals with thicker fat layers may decompose more slowly than those with leaner bodies. Extrapolating data from human studies, or even from domestic pigs, is often unreliable. The thick skin of wild boars affects the decomposition process compared to pigs. This affects how moisture and environmental elements interact with the carcass, slowing decomposition.

- Unpredictable scavenger and insect activity: the extreme environmental variability in which wild boar exist in Europe determines unpredictable scavenger and insect activity, as well as cannibalistic behaviour. Wild boar carcasses are subject to intense scavenging by various animals, which disrupts decomposition patterns and removes or alters evidence. The presence of insect larvae, particularly blowflies, can be used to estimate the minimum post-mortem interval (PMI). However, the level of insect activity (forensic entomology) varies significantly depending on geographic location, season and local insect populations. Therefore, the timing and composition of insect colonisation can be highly unpredictable. This variability in insect activity means that this method is more accurate in controlled environments and experimental studies under certain conditions.

5.2.3 Current knowledge gaps

The ability to carry out precise post-mortem investigations (PMI) on wild boar is also limited by the lack of research specific to this species. Forensic research has primarily focused on human remains and animal models, leaving a significant knowledge gap regarding wild boar decomposition and hindering the development of accurate post-mortem interval (PMI) estimation methods for diverse wildlife populations. Accessing and analysing wild boar carcasses in remote locations without (or with delayed) lab support, e.g. for entomological analysis, can further complicate the application of these methods.

Overall, although methods are available to estimate PMI in wild boar, the accuracy and precision of these estimates can be limited by the complexity and variability of the factors involved. The scarcity of baseline decomposition data for wild boar — except for recent experimental data from Germany for classical methods and the thanatometabolomic approach from Italy — makes it difficult to create accurate PMI models or timelines for wild boar across Europe. Developing and validating new methods based on an understanding of the physical and chemical changes that occur post-mortem is promising, as is combining different approaches.

Based on previous findings and discussions, we believe that determining PMI in wild boar requires various experiments and methods. These experiments often need to be conducted in various environmental settings to build a comprehensive understanding of PMI in the target species across Europe. The following are needed:

- Decomposition studies. These experiments involve placing wildlife carcasses in controlled environments (e.g., climate-controlled chambers) to monitor decomposition under specific conditions (temperature, humidity).
- Controlled environmental studies. This allows researchers to isolate and quantify the effects of individual environmental factors on decomposition rates.

Field decomposition studies would be a priority, together with the application of new methodologies such as metabolomics alongside classical methods. These studies would involve observing decomposition in natural habitats, recording environmental data such as temperature, humidity and rainfall, and documenting the stages of decomposition. Such studies are essential for understanding the impact of real-world environmental variability on

post-mortem interval (PMI) estimation. Regional experiments are needed to allow for better PMI estimation models that are adapted to specific habitats, environments, ecological characteristics and seasonal conditions. This will enable the standardisation of PMI estimation through controlled experiments, improve accuracy in real-world cases, and provide baseline data for forensic pathologists and ecologists dealing with wild boar carcasses.

6. Conclusions

6.1. Wild boar carcass search

- Twenty years have passed since the last introduction of ASF in wild boar in Europe, and detailed information on strategies and best practices for finding wild boar carcasses and adapting these methodologies locally is difficult to access. Although the timely removal of wild boar carcasses following the detection of the first case is crucial, there is a notable lack of established protocols and practical guidance for the effective detection of carcasses, especially given the variety of approaches within individual European countries due to federal or autonomous administrative structures.
- This scarcity of protocols and guidance on searching for wild boar carcasses indicates the need to make public and transfer local expertise across Europe and on focal outbreaks of ASF. Harmonising data collection and evaluating survey performance is essential in order to learn lessons and help standardise this activity.
- Relevant research has been conducted in Central Europe in relation to wild boar carcass searches and dating. These studies must be tested and adapted further in different biogeographical and epidemiological scenarios to assess their efficiency in carcass search and carcass dating, and their adaptability to different scenarios in Europe. The general principles of deathbed choice by wild boar and the methodologies that can be used are relatively well known, favouring the adoption of such protocols.
- In Europe, most of the literature on this topic comes from countries affected by ASF. Most national veterinary administrations responded that there is no systematic protocol for searching for wild boar carcasses. We advocate agreeing on and incorporating detailed guidance on wild boar carcass searches into the wild boar population control and monitoring plan that the Commission has requested from countries as part of the fight against ASF.
- The priority criteria used in the literature we surveyed to select areas for wild boar carcass searches are mainly related to the increased risk of finding dead wild boars and the estimated ASF risk. The risk determined for the target infected area, its shape and size, and the design (e.g. systematic spatial grids versus habitat-driven) will significantly impact the efficiency of carcass retrieval. The optimal approach may involve integrating different strategies to maximise effectiveness. On the one hand, a habitat-based strategy prioritises searching in areas where wild boar carcasses are most likely to be found, based on ecological and behavioural knowledge. These strategies would be more efficient in targeted areas with known wild boar activity. Grid-based strategies, on the other hand, provide comprehensive coverage and are useful in areas where habitat data is less well known. Features usually considered for a habitat-

based strategy include the presence of forests, proximity to water sources, forest types, terrain and areas with minimal human disturbance.

- One important missing step in developing carcass search strategies based on past experience is that the performance of wild boar searches was hardly ever quantified, and even worse, the methods and metrics used were not comparable. The ratio of found to hidden carcasses is mostly unknown.
- Another relevant pitfall of the currently available data is the scarcity of method comparisons, particularly fair comparisons under similar circumstances.
- An essential aspect requiring guidance concerns the efforts required and the resources available to be deployed over time. The literature on this topic is limited and lacks detail, using different metrics. This has prevented comparisons being made between methods, strategies, areas and epidemiological scenarios, and has made it difficult to determine the real efficacy in terms of the proportion of carcasses found. The parameters provided here offer some guidance on determining the necessary human effort.
- The main factors reported in the literature that may determine the applicability and performance of different wild boar carcass search protocols are of a different nature. These include natural determinants relating to wild boar ecology, the environment and climate, and how the search is organised at different stages, such as economic compensation for searchers and the means used, e.g. trained dogs and combination methods. Clearly, the relevance of different factors depends on the local scenario and the methods applied; even a given factor may diminish or increase efficacy under different circumstances.
- Surveillance and search techniques, such as active ground searches by humans or aerial surveillance, are far from 100% effective in eliminating operator fatigue and other issues. While this review identified four main methods for the active detection of wild boar carcasses, an integrated approach could improve the efficiency and effectiveness of surveillance efforts, particularly in hard-to-reach areas:
- Ground survey teams may work alongside other surveillance tools, such as drones equipped with thermal imaging cameras and carcass-detection dogs.
- Specifically, patrolling by car over known or possible hotspots for wild boar activity or death beds (risk-based surveillance) complements a more systematic search by teams of beaters, drones and dogs. This is particularly useful for making an initial, preliminary estimation of the infected area, after which more systematic search activities can be developed. The first 72 hours are crucial for effective disease control, so targeted patrolling of relevant zones is a key priority during this period.
- The use of specially trained dogs to search for carcasses is an effective tool for carcass detection, even in dense vegetation and when locating the remains of dead wild boar, such as single bones. Well-trained dogs are arguably the most portable and versatile scent detection tools currently available. However, their operational use in the field remains limited and the efficiency of odour detection can vary significantly between dogs. Appropriate biosecurity measures must also be considered when employing detection dogs.

- Further integration and generalisation of drone technology in wildlife surveillance is promising yet still underutilised. For example, drones equipped with thermal imaging cameras have been used to monitor wild boar populations, improving surveillance and containment efforts in hard-to-reach areas while offering the potential for the rapid, efficient, and safe detection of wild boar carcasses. However, there is a need to develop this technology and drone-specific protocols beyond local application.
- Searching for carcasses is time-consuming and labour-intensive, particularly in large or remote areas. Financial compensation provides a tangible incentive to motivate individuals to dedicate their time and effort to this task.
- There is no universally agreed number of carcasses that must be found to guarantee eradication. Studies indicate that only a small percentage of wild boar carcasses are typically found in natural habitats, making eradication very difficult. Despite the limited resources available, repeated searches of the same areas aim to maximise carcass detection. Rather than focusing on a specific proportion, the emphasis is placed on maximising carcass removal in conjunction with other control measures. Continuous monitoring of wild boar carcasses in affected areas is also useful for determining the exit strategy, for which precise carcass dating is relevant.
- We propose experimental areas requiring further development in order to gather applied reliable information to have elements of decision to determine the most efficient and cost-effective search strategies under different circumstances and contexts:
- Comparative search experiments should compare the effectiveness of different methods, such as human search teams versus canine search teams, systematic grid searches versus targeted searches based on habitat analysis, and the use of drones with thermal imaging versus traditional ground searches. Researchers would measure the time taken, the area covered, and the number of carcasses found by each method. Any trial must be conducted in such a way that the results can be compared between zones, using similar (or interchangeable) metrics. Such an experiment could also be carried out under real-world conditions provided specific circumstances exist that prevent wild boar from entering the searched area (e.g. areas secured with wild boar-proof fencing), thereby ensuring that no additional animals die within it and influence the carcass count relative to the initial baseline.
- To quantify the probability of detecting a wild boar carcass within a given area. This involves placing known carcasses in the field and conducting repeated searches to determine the detection rate. Factors such as the stage of carcass decomposition, vegetation cover and terrain can be varied. Several studies have analysed the spatial distribution of carcasses found in relation to environmental factors such as proximity to water sources, forest type and density, terrain, elevation and distance to roads and human settlements.
- Performance testing of trained dogs in different environments is required to evaluate how environmental conditions affect canine detection efficiency. This trial involves conducting searches in dense forests, grasslands, wetlands and mountainous areas for carcasses buried at different depths and stages of decomposition.
- Technology integration requires addressing specifically drone technology. Evaluating the effectiveness of drones equipped with thermal imaging and high-resolution cameras for

carcass detection involves conducting field trials to compare drone-based searches with ground searches.

6.2. Wild boar carcass dating

- Determining post-mortem interval (PMI) in wildlife carcasses, and in the case of wild boar, is exceptionally difficult and presents a greater challenge. Apart from some experimental studies (i.e. known PMI), there are no validated protocols or detailed guidance on dating wild boar carcasses for real-life applications. Although known experiences from Central Europe can be adapted for use in other areas, regional studies with similar methodology are still required.
- The recent development of methods such as metabolomics-based approaches is promising, but further development, as well as the appropriate facilities and expertise, is required for rapid assessment. Notably, an original case study refers to the first application of metabolomics in wild boar.
- Scientific literature on forensic techniques, mostly based on macroscopic and entomological evidence, can be transferred to different scenarios in Europe, but prior validation is required to account for prevailing environmental and ecological conditions. Estimated post-mortem interval (PMI) still presented wide ranges on the basis of experimental studies, increasing as time elapsed since death.
- Based on macroscopic evidence, the different phases of decomposition were determined variably according to the study, but they can potentially be harmonised. However, decomposition stages based mostly on macroscopic evidence cannot be universally associated with specific post-mortem intervals (PMI), as this depends on the specific context and conditions.
- While several methods are available for estimating post-mortem interval (PMI) in wild boar, the accuracy and precision of these estimates can be limited by the complexity and variability of the factors involved. The most frequently considered factors impacting PMI were season, habitat and determinants of microhabitat conditions. Environmental temperature, and specifically Accumulated Degree Days (ADD), is a parameter that is often considered to affect the process of carcass decay. Body size (or age as a proxy) as well as insect activity and scavenger activity were considered relevant throughout the decomposition process in the sampled studies.
- The main considerations that need to be accounted for when determining PMI in wild boar across Europe are:
 - Extreme environmental variability means that extrapolating data from studies in different areas/bioregions is probably unreliable.
 - Aspects related to specific decomposition processes in wild boar.
 - Extrapolating data from human studies, or even from studies of domesticated animals such as pigs, is also unreliable.
 - Unpredictable scavenger and insect activity, which varies by area/bioregion.
 - Accessing and analysing wild boar carcasses in remote locations often requires work to be done in the field without lab support (e.g. delayed entomological analysis).

- The scarcity of baseline decomposition data for wild boar, except for recent experimental data obtained using classical methods and a single metabolomic study, makes it difficult to create accurate models or timelines for post-mortem interval (PMI) estimation in wild boar across Europe.
- The development and validation of new methods based on an understanding of the metabolomic changes that occur post-mortem is promising, as is the combination of different approaches.
- In summary, determining PMI in wild boar requires various experiments to be conducted in different environmental settings to develop a comprehensive understanding of PMI across Europe. This includes decomposition and controlled environmental studies. Field decomposition studies are a priority, as is the application of new methodologies such as metabolomics alongside classical methods. Conducting regional experiments to develop better PMI estimation models adapted to specific habitats, environments, ecological characteristics and seasonal conditions will enable the standardisation of PMI and improve the accuracy of estimation in real-world cases. This will also provide the necessary baseline data for forensic pathologists and ecologists dealing with wild boar carcasses.

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spectrometry (DART-HRMS), *Microchemical Journal*, 212, 2025, 113296,
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Annexes

Annex 1. Carcass search final selection (n=60 papers*method)

Type document	Title	Authors	Source title	Year publication	Country
Research article	Detection of African swine fever virus in free-ranging wild boar in Southeast Asia	Denstedt E et al.		2021	Laos, Cambodia, Vietnam
Blog or grey	Blog or grey	Blog or grey	Blog or grey	2024	Italy
Research article	Strategic Challenges to the Eradication of African Swine Fever Genotype II in Domestic Pigs in North Italy	Pavone et al.		2024	Italy
Blog or grey	Blog or grey	Blog or grey	Blog or grey	2022	South Korea
Blog or grey	Blog or grey	Blog or grey	Blog or grey	2022	Germany
Interview	Interview	Mario Chiari, Francesca Meriggi	Protocols implemented in Regione Lombardia		Italy
Interview	Interview	Mario Chiari, Francesca Meriggi			Italy
Interview	Interview	Mario Chiari, Francesca Meriggi			Italy
Interview	Interview	Mario Chiari, Francesca Meriggi			Italy
Interview	Interview	Mario Chiari, Francesca Meriggi			Italy
Interview	Interview	Mario Chiari, Francesca Meriggi			Italy
Interview	Interview	Interview	Interview		Italy

Interview	Interview	Interview	Interview		Italy
Research article	First Outbreak of African Swine Fever in Sweden: Local Epidemiology, Surveillance, and Eradication Strategies	Chenais, E et al.	Transboundary and Emerging Diseases	2024	Sweden
Interview	Interview	Interview	Interview		Italy
Interview	Interview	Interview	Interview		Italy
Interview	Interview	Interview	Interview		Italy
Interview	Interview	Interview	Interview		Italy
Interview	Interview	Interview	Interview		Italy
Interview	Interview	Interview	Interview		Poland
Interview	Interview	Interview	Interview		Poland
Interview	Interview	Interview	Interview		South Korea
Research article	African swine fever in wild boar, South Korea, 2019	Jo, Yeong-Seok, Gortázar, Christian			South Korea
Research article	African Swine Fever in wild boar: Assessing interventions in South Korea				South Korea
Research article	Remote Sensing Provides a Rapid Epidemiological Context for the Control of African Swine Fever in Germany				Germany
Research article					Germany
Research article	The possibilities and limitations of thermal imaging to detect wild boar (<i>Sus scrofa</i>) carcasses as a strategy for managing African Swine Fever (ASF) outbreaks	Hohmann, U et al.	Berliner und Münchener Tierärztliche Wochenschrift	2021	Germany
Research article	Research priorities to fill knowledge gaps in wild boar management measures that could improve the control of African swine fever in wild boar populations				Germany

Research article	Application of forward-looking infrared (FLIR) imaging from an unmanned aerial platform in the search for decomposing remains	Butter et al.	J Forensic Sci	20221	Australia
Questionnaire	Questionnaire	Questionnaire	Questionnaire		Finland
Questionnaire	Questionnaire	Questionnaire	Questionnaire		Slovenia
Research article	Drone-Based Thermal Imaging in the Detection of Wildlife Carcasses and Disease Management	Rietz, J et al.	Transboundary and Emerging Diseases	2023	Germany
Research article	Epidemiological analysis of African swine fever in the European Union (September 2019 to August 2020)	Desmecht et al.	EFSA Journal	2021	Poland
Research article	Epidemiological analysis of two first cases of African swine fever in wild boar in Poland	Pejsak, Z et al.	Medycyna Weterynaryjna	2014	Poland
Research article	Passive Surveillance as a Key Tool for African Swine Fever Eradication in Wild Boar: A Protocol to Find Carcasses Tested and Validated in the Mediterranean Island of Sardinia	Coradduzza, E et al.	Viruses	2024	Italy
Research article	Management of a Focal Introduction of ASF Virus in Wild Boar: The Belgian Experience	Licoppe, et al.	Pathogens	2023	Belgium
Research article	Scavenger-induced scattering of wild boar carcasses over large distances and its implications for disease management	Rietz et al.	Journal of Environmental Management	2024	Germany
Research article	Season, decay stage, habitat, temperature and carrion beetles allow estimating the post-mortem interval of wild boar carcasses	Müller, J. et al.	Ecological Solutions and Evidence	2024	Germany

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Blog or grey	Blog 1.- zusammenfassende- allgemeinverfuegung- sperzone-ii				Germany
Blog or grey	Blog				Greece
Blog or grey	Blog or grey	Blog or grey	Blog or grey		Czech Republic
Blog or grey	Blog or grey	Blog or grey	Blog or grey		Germany
Research article	How to Strengthen Wildlife Surveillance to Support Freedom From Disease: Example of ASF Surveillance in France, at the Border With an Infected Area			2021	France
Research article	How to Strengthen Wildlife Surveillance to Support Freedom From Disease: Example of ASF Surveillance in France, at the Border With an Infected Area			2021	France
Research article	Drohnen im Einsatz gegen Afrikanische Schweinepest				Germany
Research article	Bekämpfung der Afrikanischen Schweinepest bei Wildschweinen				Germany
Research article	Use of Dogs With Electronic Tracking Equipment for Searching for the Carcasses of Wild Boars	Havránek, F et al.	Zpravy Lesnickeho Vyzkumu	2020	Czech Republic
Interview	Schleswig-Holstein, administrative district: Herzogtum Lauenburg	Interview	Interview		Germany
Interview	mainly Baden- Württemberg	Interview	Interview		Germany
Interview	Schleswig-Holstein, administrative district: Segeberg	Interview	Interview		Germany
Interview	Brandenburg	Interview	Interview		Germany
Interview	Brandenburg, Spree-Neiße district	Interview	Interview		Germany

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Interview	Schleswig-Holstein, administrative district: Herzogtum Lauenburg	Interview	Interview		Germany
Interview	Baden-Württemberg and Hesse	Interview	Interview		Germany
Research article	Management of a Focal Introduction of ASF Virus in Wild Boar: The Belgian Experience	Licoppe, A et al..	Pathogens	2023	Belgium
Research article	Massive death of wild boars caused by ethylene glycol: a case report	Siroka, et al	Veterinarni Medicina	2014	Czech Republic
Research article	Modelling the Spatial Distribution of ASF-Positive Wild Boar Carcasses in South Korea Using 2019–2020 National Surveillance Data	Lim et al.	Animals	2021	South Korea
Research article	Key risk factors and impact of African swine fever spreading on pig production in Serbia	Polaček et al	Acta Veterinaria	2021	Serbia
Blog or grey	Blog or grey	Blog or grey	Blog or grey		Poland
Blog or grey	Blog or grey	Blog or grey	Blog or grey		Germany

Annex 2. Carcass dating final selection (n=11)

Type of document	Title	Authors	Journal	Year	Country	Original or reproduced	Reproduced from
Scientific paper	Unravelling the dispersal dynamics and ecological drivers of the African swine fever outbreak in Belgium	Dellicour Simon et al.	J Appl Ecol. 2020	2020	Belgium	R	Brooks et al. 2018, Probst et al. 2020
Scientific paper	First outbreak of African swine fever in Sweden: local epidemiology, surveillance, and eradication strategies	Chenais Erika et al.	Transboundary and Emerging Diseases	2024	Sweden	R	Megyesi et al. 2005
Scientific paper	Spatio-temporal epidemiology of the spread of African swine fever in wild boar and the role of environmental factors in South Korea	Ito Satoshi et al.	Viruses 2022, 14 (12), 2779	2022	South Korea	R	Parsons HR. 2009, Probst et al. 2020. Keough et al, 17.
Scientific paper	drone-based thermal imaging in the detection of wildlife carcasses and disease management	Janine Rietz et al.	Transboundary and Emerging Diseases Volume 2023, Article ID 5517000,	2023	Germany	R	Goff 2009, Anderson and Van Laerhoven 1996
Scientific paper	Estimating the <i>postmortem</i> interval of wild boar carcasses	Carolina Probst et al.	Vet Sci 2020 Jan 5;7(1):6.	2020	Germany	R	Megyesi et al. 2005

Scientific paper	Season, decay stage, habitat, temperature and carrion beetles allow estimating the post-mortem interval of wild boar carcasses	Müller et al.	Ecological Solutions and Evidence 5(1):12305	2024	Germany	R	Goff 2009, Anderson and Van Laerhoven 1996, Von Hoermann et al. 2018
Scientific paper	Thanatometabolomics in wildlife: identifying potential metabolic markers of post-mortem intervals in wild boars by direct analysis in real time High Resolution Mass Spectrometry (Dart-Hrms)	Zacometti, Carmela et al.	Microchemical Journal 212:113-296	2024	Italy	O	
Scientific paper	Wildlife as potential vectors of African swine fever virus	Lim, Sang Jin et al.	Journal of Forest and Environmental Science, Vol. 38, No. 1, pp. 55-63, March, 2022	2022	South Korea	R	Parsons HR. 2009, Probst et al. 2020; Keough et al. 17.
Scientific paper	Functional differences in scavenger communities and the speed of carcass decomposition	Wenting, Elke et al.	Ecology and Evolution, 2022;12:e8576	2022	Netherlands	O	
Scientific paper	A preliminary investigation into the decomposition rate of wild boar carcasses in forest habitats	Hee-Kyeong Cho et al.	J. Prev. Vet. Med. 2021; 45(1): 44-52.	2021	South Korea	R	Megyesi et al. 2005

Other output	Grey literature: notes about the DEATHBOARS project	Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale delle Venezie (IZSVe)	Presentation	2024	Italy	R	Pittner et al. 2020, Probst et al. 2020
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